

Miscellaneous 22 Dimensional Functions

`Solve[2 π r - 2 π x == ψ j, r]`

$$\left\{ \left\{ r \rightarrow \frac{2 \pi x + j \psi}{2 \pi} \right\} \right\}$$

`Solve[2 π r - 2 π x == ψ j, x]`

$$\left\{ \left\{ x \rightarrow \frac{2 \pi r - j \psi}{2 \pi} \right\} \right\}$$

`Solve[2 π r - 2 π x == ψ j, j]`

$$\left\{ \left\{ j \rightarrow \frac{2 (\pi r - \pi x)}{\psi} \right\} \right\}$$

`Solve[2 π r - 2 π x == ψ j, ψ]`

$$\left\{ \left\{ \psi \rightarrow \frac{2 (\pi r - \pi x)}{j} \right\} \right\}$$

`Solve[2 π r - 2 π √r^2 - h^2 == ψ j, h]`

$$\left\{ \left\{ h \rightarrow -\frac{\sqrt{4 j \pi r \psi - j^2 \psi^2}}{2 \pi} \right\}, \left\{ h \rightarrow \frac{\sqrt{4 j \pi r \psi - j^2 \psi^2}}{2 \pi} \right\} \right\}$$

`ContourPlot3D[ $\frac{\sqrt{4 j \pi r \psi - j^2 \psi^2}}{2 \pi}$ , {r, -1, 1}, {j, -1, 1}, {ψ, -2 π, 2 π}]`

v / t =

$$\begin{aligned} j / (\psi / (2\pi)) &= (j\psi) / ((\psi / (2\pi))^2) == (2\pi r - 2\pi \sqrt{r^2 - h^2}) / ((\psi / (2\pi))^2) == \\ & \left(2\pi r - 2\pi \sqrt{r^2 - \frac{\sqrt{4j\pi r\psi - j^2\psi^2}}{2\pi}} \right) / ((\psi / (2\pi))^2) == \\ & - \frac{(4j\pi r - 2j^2\psi)(4\pi r\psi - 2j\psi^2)}{8\pi(4j\pi r\psi - j^2\psi^2)^{3/2}} + \frac{4\pi r - 4j\psi}{4\pi\sqrt{4j\pi r\psi - j^2\psi^2}} \end{aligned}$$

Solve[(2\pi r - 2\pi x) / ((\psi / (2\pi))^2) ==

$$\begin{aligned} & - \frac{(4j\pi r - 2j^2\psi)(4\pi r\psi - 2j\psi^2)}{8\pi(4j\pi r\psi - j^2\psi^2)^{3/2}} + \frac{4\pi r - 4j\psi}{4\pi\sqrt{4j\pi r\psi - j^2\psi^2}}, j] \\ \{j \rightarrow \frac{3\pi r}{\psi} - \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{\left(\frac{36\pi^2 r^2}{\psi^2} - \frac{4(3072\pi^{10}r^4 - 6144\pi^{10}r^3x + 3072\pi^{10}r^2x^2 + 11\pi^2r^2\psi^4)}{\psi^2(256\pi^8r^2 - 512\pi^8rx + 256\pi^8x^2 + \psi^4)} \right)} - \right. \\ & \frac{4(3072\pi^{10}r^4\psi - 6144\pi^{10}r^3x\psi + 3072\pi^{10}r^2x^2\psi + 11\pi^2r^2\psi^5)}{3(-256\pi^8r^2\psi^3 + 512\pi^8rx\psi^3 - 256\pi^8x^2\psi^3 - \psi^7)} + \\ & \left. \frac{(16 \times 2^{1/3} \pi^4 (6144\pi^8r^6\psi^6 - 12288\pi^8r^5x\psi^6 + 6144\pi^8r^4x^2\psi^6 + 25r^4\psi^{10}))}{(3(-256\pi^8r^2\psi^3 + 512\pi^8rx\psi^3 - 256\pi^8x^2\psi^3 - \psi^7)} \right) \\ & \left(-452984832\pi^{22}r^{10}\psi^7 + 1811939328\pi^{22}r^9x\psi^7 - 2717908992\pi^{22}r^8x^2\psi^7 + \right. \\ & \quad \psi^7 + 1811939328\pi^{22}r^7x^3\psi^7 - 452984832\pi^{22}r^6x^4\psi^7 - 5898240\pi^{14}r^8 \\ & \quad \psi^{11} + 11796480\pi^{14}r^7x\psi^{11} - 5898240\pi^{14}r^6x^2\psi^{11} - 16000\pi^6r^6\psi^{15} + \\ & \quad \left. \sqrt{(205195258022068224\pi^{44}r^{20}\psi^{14} - 1641562064176545792\pi^{44}r^{19}x\psi^{14} + \right. \\ & \quad 5745467224617910272\pi^{44}r^{18}x^2\psi^{14} - 11490934449235820544 \\ & \quad \pi^{44}r^{17}x^3\psi^{14} + 14363668061544775680\pi^{44}r^{16}x^4\psi^{14} - \\ & \quad 11490934449235820544\pi^{44}r^{15}x^5\psi^{14} + 5745467224617910272\pi^{44}r^{14} \\ & \quad x^6\psi^{14} - 1641562064176545792\pi^{44}r^{13}x^7\psi^{14} + 205195258022068224 \\ & \quad \pi^{44}r^{12}x^8\psi^{14} + 1543714325397504\pi^{36}r^{18}\psi^{18} - 9262285952385024\pi^{36} \\ & \quad r^{17}x\psi^{18} + 23155714880962560\pi^{36}r^{16}x^2\psi^{18} - 30874286507950080\pi^{36} \\ & \quad r^{15}x^3\psi^{18} + 23155714880962560\pi^{36}r^{14}x^4\psi^{18} - 9262285952385024\pi^{36} \\ & \quad r^{13}x^5\psi^{18} + 1543714325397504\pi^{36}r^{12}x^6\psi^{18} + 2899102924800\pi^{28}r^{16} \\ & \quad \psi^{22} - 11596411699200\pi^{28}r^{15}x\psi^{22} + 17394617548800\pi^{28}r^{14}x^2\psi^{22} - \\ & \quad \left. 11596411699200\pi^{28}r^{13}x^3\psi^{22} + 2899102924800\pi^{28}r^{12}x^4\psi^{22}) \right)^{1/3} \Bigg) + \\ & \left(-452984832\pi^{22}r^{10}\psi^7 + 1811939328\pi^{22}r^9x\psi^7 - 2717908992\pi^{22}r^8x^2\psi^7 + \right. \\ & \quad 1811939328\pi^{22}r^7x^3\psi^7 - 452984832\pi^{22}r^6x^4\psi^7 - 5898240\pi^{14}r^8 \\ & \quad \psi^{11} + 11796480\pi^{14}r^7x\psi^{11} - 5898240\pi^{14}r^6x^2\psi^{11} - 16000\pi^6r^6\psi^{15} + \\ & \quad \left. \sqrt{(205195258022068224\pi^{44}r^{20}\psi^{14} - 1641562064176545792\pi^{44}r^{19}x\psi^{14} + \right. \\ & \quad 5745467224617910272\pi^{44}r^{18}x^2\psi^{14} - 11490934449235820544\pi^{44}r^{17}x^3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left(\pi^{44} r^{15} x^5 \psi^{14} + 5\,745\,467\,224\,617\,910\,272 \pi^{44} r^{14} x^6 \psi^{14} - \right. \\
 & 1\,641\,562\,064\,176\,545\,792 \pi^{44} r^{13} x^7 \psi^{14} + 205\,195\,258\,022\,068\,224 \pi^{44} r^{12} \\
 & x^8 \psi^{14} + 1\,543\,714\,325\,397\,504 \pi^{36} r^{18} \psi^{18} - 9\,262\,285\,952\,385\,024 \pi^{36} r^{17} x \psi^{18} + \\
 & 23\,155\,714\,880\,962\,560 \pi^{36} r^{16} x^2 \psi^{18} - 30\,874\,286\,507\,950\,080 \pi^{36} r^{15} x^3 \psi^{18} + \\
 & 23\,155\,714\,880\,962\,560 \pi^{36} r^{14} x^4 \psi^{18} - 9\,262\,285\,952\,385\,024 \pi^{36} r^{13} x^5 \psi^{18} + \\
 & 1\,543\,714\,325\,397\,504 \pi^{36} r^{12} x^6 \psi^{18} + 2\,899\,102\,924\,800 \pi^{28} r^{16} \psi^{22} - \\
 & 11\,596\,411\,699\,200 \pi^{28} r^{15} x \psi^{22} + 17\,394\,617\,548\,800 \pi^{28} r^{14} x^2 \psi^{22} - \\
 & \left. 11\,596\,411\,699\,200 \pi^{28} r^{13} x^3 \psi^{22} + 2\,899\,102\,924\,800 \pi^{28} r^{12} x^4 \psi^{22} \right)^{1/3} / \\
 & \left(3 \times 2^{1/3} \left(-256 \pi^8 r^2 \psi^3 + 512 \pi^8 r x \psi^3 - 256 \pi^8 x^2 \psi^3 - \psi^7 \right) \right) - \\
 & \left(\frac{1728 \pi^3 r^3}{\psi^3} - \frac{192 \pi r \left(3072 \pi^{10} r^4 - 6144 \pi^{10} r^3 x + 3072 \pi^{10} r^2 x^2 + 11 \pi^2 r^2 \psi^4 \right)}{\psi^3 \left(256 \pi^8 r^2 - 512 \pi^8 r x + 256 \pi^8 x^2 + \psi^4 \right)} + \right. \\
 & \left. \frac{128 \left(1024 \pi^{11} r^5 - 2048 \pi^{11} r^4 x + 1024 \pi^{11} r^3 x^2 + 3 \pi^3 r^3 \psi^4 \right)}{\psi^3 \left(256 \pi^8 r^2 - 512 \pi^8 r x + 256 \pi^8 x^2 + \psi^4 \right)} \right) / \\
 & \left(4 \sqrt[4]{\left(\frac{36 \pi^2 r^2}{\psi^2} - \frac{4 \left(3072 \pi^{10} r^4 - 6144 \pi^{10} r^3 x + 3072 \pi^{10} r^2 x^2 + 11 \pi^2 r^2 \psi^4 \right)}{\psi^2 \left(256 \pi^8 r^2 - 512 \pi^8 r x + 256 \pi^8 x^2 + \psi^4 \right)} - \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left(4 \left(3072 \pi^{10} r^4 \psi - 6144 \pi^{10} r^3 x \psi + 3072 \pi^{10} r^2 x^2 \psi + 11 \pi^2 r^2 \psi^5 \right) \right) / \right. \\
 & \left. \left(3 \left(-256 \pi^8 r^2 \psi^3 + 512 \pi^8 r x \psi^3 - 256 \pi^8 x^2 \psi^3 - \psi^7 \right) \right) + \right. \\
 & \left. \left(16 \times 2^{1/3} \pi^4 \left(6144 \pi^8 r^6 \psi^6 - 12\,288 \pi^8 r^5 x \psi^6 + 6144 \pi^8 r^4 x^2 \psi^6 + 25 r^4 \psi^{10} \right) \right) \right) / \\
 & \left(3 \left(-256 \pi^8 r^2 \psi^3 + 512 \pi^8 r x \psi^3 - 256 \pi^8 x^2 \psi^3 - \psi^7 \right) \right. \\
 & \left. \left(-452\,984\,832 \pi^{22} r^{10} \psi^7 + 1\,811\,939\,328 \pi^{22} r^9 x \psi^7 - 2\,717\,908\,992 \pi^{22} \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. r^8 x^2 \psi^7 + 1\,811\,939\,328 \pi^{22} r^7 x^3 \psi^7 - 452\,984\,832 \pi^{22} r^6 x^4 \psi^7 - \right. \right. \\
 & \left. 5\,898\,240 \pi^{14} r^8 \psi^{11} + 11\,796\,480 \pi^{14} r^7 x \psi^{11} - 5\,898\,240 \pi^{14} r^6 x^2 \psi^{11} - \right. \\
 & \left. 16\,000 \pi^6 r^6 \psi^{15} + \sqrt{\left(205\,195\,258\,022\,068\,224 \pi^{44} r^{20} \psi^{14} - \right. \right. \\
 & 1\,641\,562\,064\,176\,545\,792 \pi^{44} r^{19} x \psi^{14} + 5\,745\,467\,224\,617\,910\,272 \\
 & \pi^{44} r^{18} x^2 \psi^{14} - 11\,490\,934\,449\,235\,820\,544 \pi^{44} r^{17} \\
 & x^3 \psi^{14} + 14\,363\,668\,061\,544\,775\,680 \pi^{44} r^{16} x^4 \psi^{14} - \\
 & 11\,490\,934\,449\,235\,820\,544 \pi^{44} r^{15} x^5 \psi^{14} + 5\,745\,467\,224\,617\,910\,272 \\
 & \pi^{44} r^{14} x^6 \psi^{14} - 1\,641\,562\,064\,176\,545\,792 \pi^{44} r^{13} x^7 \psi^{14} + \\
 & 205\,195\,258\,022\,068\,224 \pi^{44} r^{12} x^8 \psi^{14} + 1\,543\,714\,325\,397\,504 \pi^{36} r^{18} \\
 & \psi^{18} - 9\,262\,285\,952\,385\,024 \pi^{36} r^{17} x \psi^{18} + 23\,155\,714\,880\,962\,560 \\
 & \pi^{36} r^{16} x^2 \psi^{18} - 30\,874\,286\,507\,950\,080 \pi^{36} r^{15} x^3 \psi^{18} + \\
 & 23\,155\,714\,880\,962\,560 \pi^{36} r^{14} x^4 \psi^{18} - 9\,262\,285\,952\,385\,024 \\
 & \pi^{36} r^{13} x^5 \psi^{18} + 1\,543\,714\,325\,397\,504 \pi^{36} r^{12} x^6 \psi^{18} + \\
 & 2\,899\,102\,924\,800 \pi^{28} r^{16} \psi^{22} - 11\,596\,411\,699\,200 \pi^{28} r^{15} x \psi^{22} + \\
 & 17\,394\,617\,548\,800 \pi^{28} r^{14} x^2 \psi^{22} - 11\,596\,411\,699\,200 \\
 & \left. \left. \pi^{28} r^{13} x^3 \psi^{22} + 2\,899\,102\,924\,800 \pi^{28} r^{12} x^4 \psi^{22} \right) \right)^{1/3} \left. \right) + \\
 & \left(-452\,984\,832 \pi^{22} r^{10} \psi^7 + 1\,811\,939\,328 \pi^{22} r^9 x \psi^7 - 2\,717\,908\,992 \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \psi^{18} - 9\,262\,285\,952\,385\,024\,\pi^{36}r^{17}x\psi^{18} + 23\,155\,714\,880\,962\,560 \\
 & \pi^{36}r^{16}x^2\psi^{18} - 30\,874\,286\,507\,950\,080\,\pi^{36}r^{15}x^3\psi^{18} + \\
 & 23\,155\,714\,880\,962\,560\,\pi^{36}r^{14}x^4\psi^{18} - 9\,262\,285\,952\,385\,024 \\
 & \pi^{36}r^{13}x^5\psi^{18} + 1\,543\,714\,325\,397\,504\,\pi^{36}r^{12}x^6\psi^{18} + \\
 & 2\,899\,102\,924\,800\,\pi^{28}r^{16}\psi^{22} - 11\,596\,411\,699\,200\,\pi^{28}r^{15}x\psi^{22} + \\
 & 17\,394\,617\,548\,800\,\pi^{28}r^{14}x^2\psi^{22} - 11\,596\,411\,699\,200 \\
 & \pi^{28}r^{13}x^3\psi^{22} + 2\,899\,102\,924\,800\,\pi^{28}r^{12}x^4\psi^{22} \Big)^{1/3} \Big) + \\
 & \left(-452\,984\,832\,\pi^{22}r^{10}\psi^7 + 1\,811\,939\,328\,\pi^{22}r^9x\psi^7 - 2\,717\,908\,992 \right. \\
 & \left. \pi^{22}r^8x^2\psi^7 + 1\,811\,939\,328\,\pi^{22}r^7x^3\psi^7 - 452\,984\,832\,\pi^{22}r^6x^4\psi^7 - \right. \\
 & \left. 5\,898\,240\,\pi^{14}r^8\psi^{11} + 11\,796\,480\,\pi^{14}r^7x\psi^{11} - 5\,898\,240\,\pi^{14}r^6x^2\psi^{11} - \right. \\
 & \left. 16\,000\,\pi^6r^6\psi^{15} + \sqrt{\left(205\,195\,258\,022\,068\,224\,\pi^{44}r^{20}\psi^{14} - \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 1\,641\,562\,064\,176\,545\,792\,\pi^{44}r^{19}x\psi^{14} + 5\,745\,467\,224\,617\,910\,272 \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. \pi^{44}r^{18}x^2\psi^{14} - 11\,490\,934\,449\,235\,820\,544\,\pi^{44}r^{17}x^3\psi^{14} + \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 14\,363\,668\,061\,544\,775\,680\,\pi^{44}r^{16}x^4\psi^{14} - 11\,490\,934\,449\,235\,820\,544 \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. \pi^{44}r^{15}x^5\psi^{14} + 5\,745\,467\,224\,617\,910\,272\,\pi^{44}r^{14}x^6\psi^{14} - \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 1\,641\,562\,064\,176\,545\,792\,\pi^{44}r^{13}x^7\psi^{14} + 205\,195\,258\,022\,068\,224\,\pi^{44} \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. r^{12}x^8\psi^{14} + 1\,543\,714\,325\,397\,504\,\pi^{36}r^{18}\psi^{18} - 9\,262\,285\,952\,385\,024 \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. \pi^{36}r^{17}x\psi^{18} + 23\,155\,714\,880\,962\,560\,\pi^{36}r^{16}x^2\psi^{18} - \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. 30\,874\,286\,507\,950\,080\,\pi^{36}r^{15}x^3\psi^{18} + 23\,155\,714\,880\,962\,560\,\pi^{36}r^{14} \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. x^4\psi^{18} - 9\,262\,285\,952\,385\,024\,\pi^{36}r^{13}x^5\psi^{18} + 1\,543\,714\,325\,397\,504 \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. \pi^{36}r^{12}x^6\psi^{18} + 2\,899\,102\,924\,800\,\pi^{28}r^{16}\psi^{22} - 11\,596\,411\,699\,200 \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. \pi^{28}r^{15}x\psi^{22} + 17\,394\,617\,548\,800\,\pi^{28}r^{14}x^2\psi^{22} - 11\,596\,411\,699\,200 \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. \pi^{28}r^{13}x^3\psi^{22} + 2\,899\,102\,924\,800\,\pi^{28}r^{12}x^4\psi^{22} \right) \right)^{1/3} \Big) / \\
 & \left. \left. \left. \left(3 \times 2^{1/3} \left(-256\,\pi^8r^2\psi^3 + 512\,\pi^8rx\psi^3 - 256\,\pi^8x^2\psi^3 - \psi^7 \right) \right) \right) \right) \Big\} , \\
 & \left\{ j \rightarrow \frac{3\pi r}{\psi} + \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{\left(\frac{36\pi^2r^2}{\psi^2} - \frac{4(3072\pi^{10}r^4 - 6144\pi^{10}r^3x + 3072\pi^{10}r^2x^2 + 11\pi^2r^2\psi^4)}{\psi^2(256\pi^8r^2 - 512\pi^8rx + 256\pi^8x^2 + \psi^4)} \right)} - \right. \\
 & \left. \frac{4(3072\pi^{10}r^4\psi - 6144\pi^{10}r^3x\psi + 3072\pi^{10}r^2x^2\psi + 11\pi^2r^2\psi^5)}{3(-256\pi^8r^2\psi^3 + 512\pi^8rx\psi^3 - 256\pi^8x^2\psi^3 - \psi^7)} + \right. \\
 & \left. (16 \times 2^{1/3} \pi^4 \right. \\
 & \left. (6144\pi^8r^6\psi^6 - 12\,288\pi^8r^5x\psi^6 + 6144\pi^8r^4x^2\psi^6 + 25r^4\psi^{10}) \right) \Big/ \\
 & \left(3(-256\pi^8r^2\psi^3 + 512\pi^8rx\psi^3 - 256\pi^8x^2\psi^3 - \psi^7) \right. \\
 & \left. (-452\,984\,832\,\pi^{22}r^{10}\psi^7 + 1\,811\,939\,328\,\pi^{22}r^9x\psi^7 - 2\,717\,908\,992\,\pi^{22}r^8x^2 \right. \\
 & \left. \psi^7 + 1\,811\,939\,328\,\pi^{22}r^7x^3\psi^7 - 452\,984\,832\,\pi^{22}r^6x^4\psi^7 - 5\,898\,240\,\pi^{14} \right. \\
 & \left. r^8\psi^{11} + 11\,796\,480\,\pi^{14}r^7x\psi^{11} - 5\,898\,240\,\pi^{14}r^6x^2\psi^{11} - 16\,000\,\pi^6r^6 \right. \\
 & \left. \psi^{15} + \sqrt{\left(205\,195\,258\,022\,068\,224\,\pi^{44}r^{20}\psi^{14} - 1\,641\,562\,064\,176\,545\,792 \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. \pi^{44}r^{19}x\psi^{14} + 5\,745\,467\,224\,617\,910\,272\,\pi^{44}r^{18}x^2\psi^{14} - \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. \right. \right.
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 11\,490\,934\,449\,235\,820\,544\,\pi^{44} r^{17} x^3 \psi^{14} + 14\,363\,668\,061\,544\,775\,680 \\
 & \pi^{44} r^{16} x^4 \psi^{14} - 11\,490\,934\,449\,235\,820\,544\,\pi^{44} r^{15} x^5 \psi^{14} + \\
 & 5\,745\,467\,224\,617\,910\,272\,\pi^{44} r^{14} x^6 \psi^{14} - 1\,641\,562\,064\,176\,545\,792 \\
 & \pi^{44} r^{13} x^7 \psi^{14} + 205\,195\,258\,022\,068\,224\,\pi^{44} r^{12} x^8 \psi^{14} + \\
 & 1\,543\,714\,325\,397\,504\,\pi^{36} r^{18} \psi^{18} - 9\,262\,285\,952\,385\,024\,\pi^{36} r^{17} x \psi^{18} + \\
 & 23\,155\,714\,880\,962\,560\,\pi^{36} r^{16} x^2 \psi^{18} - 30\,874\,286\,507\,950\,080\,\pi^{36} r^{15} x^3 \psi^{18} + \\
 & 23\,155\,714\,880\,962\,560\,\pi^{36} r^{14} x^4 \psi^{18} - 9\,262\,285\,952\,385\,024\,\pi^{36} r^{13} x^5 \psi^{18} + \\
 & 1\,543\,714\,325\,397\,504\,\pi^{36} r^{12} x^6 \psi^{18} + 2\,899\,102\,924\,800\,\pi^{28} r^{16} \psi^{22} - \\
 & 11\,596\,411\,699\,200\,\pi^{28} r^{15} x \psi^{22} + 17\,394\,617\,548\,800\,\pi^{28} r^{14} x^2 \psi^{22} - \\
 & 11\,596\,411\,699\,200\,\pi^{28} r^{13} x^3 \psi^{22} + 2\,899\,102\,924\,800\,\pi^{28} r^{12} x^4 \psi^{22} \Big)^{1/3} \Big) + \\
 & \left(-452\,984\,832\,\pi^{22} r^{10} \psi^7 + 1\,811\,939\,328\,\pi^{22} r^9 x \psi^7 - 2\,717\,908\,992\,\pi^{22} r^8 x^2 \psi^7 + \right. \\
 & 1\,811\,939\,328\,\pi^{22} r^7 x^3 \psi^7 - 452\,984\,832\,\pi^{22} r^6 x^4 \psi^7 - 5\,898\,240\,\pi^{14} r^8 \psi^{11} + \\
 & 11\,796\,480\,\pi^{14} r^7 x \psi^{11} - 5\,898\,240\,\pi^{14} r^6 x^2 \psi^{11} - 16\,000\,\pi^6 r^6 \psi^{15} + \\
 & \sqrt{ \left(205\,195\,258\,022\,068\,224\,\pi^{44} r^{20} \psi^{14} - 1\,641\,562\,064\,176\,545\,792\,\pi^{44} r^{19} x \psi^{14} + \right. \\
 & 5\,745\,467\,224\,617\,910\,272\,\pi^{44} r^{18} x^2 \psi^{14} - 11\,490\,934\,449\,235\,820\,544\,\pi^{44} r^{17} x^3 \\
 & \psi^{14} + 14\,363\,668\,061\,544\,775\,680\,\pi^{44} r^{16} x^4 \psi^{14} - 11\,490\,934\,449\,235\,820\,544 \\
 & \pi^{44} r^{15} x^5 \psi^{14} + 5\,745\,467\,224\,617\,910\,272\,\pi^{44} r^{14} x^6 \psi^{14} - \\
 & 1\,641\,562\,064\,176\,545\,792\,\pi^{44} r^{13} x^7 \psi^{14} + 205\,195\,258\,022\,068\,224\,\pi^{44} r^{12} \\
 & x^8 \psi^{14} + 1\,543\,714\,325\,397\,504\,\pi^{36} r^{18} \psi^{18} - 9\,262\,285\,952\,385\,024\,\pi^{36} r^{17} x \psi^{18} + \\
 & 23\,155\,714\,880\,962\,560\,\pi^{36} r^{16} x^2 \psi^{18} - 30\,874\,286\,507\,950\,080\,\pi^{36} r^{15} x^3 \psi^{18} + \\
 & 23\,155\,714\,880\,962\,560\,\pi^{36} r^{14} x^4 \psi^{18} - 9\,262\,285\,952\,385\,024\,\pi^{36} r^{13} x^5 \psi^{18} + \\
 & 1\,543\,714\,325\,397\,504\,\pi^{36} r^{12} x^6 \psi^{18} + 2\,899\,102\,924\,800\,\pi^{28} r^{16} \psi^{22} - \\
 & 11\,596\,411\,699\,200\,\pi^{28} r^{15} x \psi^{22} + 17\,394\,617\,548\,800\,\pi^{28} r^{14} x^2 \psi^{22} - \\
 & \left. \left. 11\,596\,411\,699\,200\,\pi^{28} r^{13} x^3 \psi^{22} + 2\,899\,102\,924\,800\,\pi^{28} r^{12} x^4 \psi^{22} \right) \right)^{1/3} \Big/ \\
 & \left. \left(3 \times 2^{1/3} \left(-256\,\pi^8 r^2 \psi^3 + 512\,\pi^8 r x \psi^3 - 256\,\pi^8 x^2 \psi^3 - \psi^7 \right) \right) \right) - \\
 & \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{ \left(\frac{72\,\pi^2 r^2}{\psi^2} - \frac{4 \left(3072\,\pi^{10} r^4 - 6144\,\pi^{10} r^3 x + 3072\,\pi^{10} r^2 x^2 + 11\,\pi^2 r^2 \psi^4 \right)}{\psi^2 \left(256\,\pi^8 r^2 - 512\,\pi^8 r x + 256\,\pi^8 x^2 + \psi^4 \right)} + \right. \\
 & \frac{4 \left(3072\,\pi^{10} r^4 \psi - 6144\,\pi^{10} r^3 x \psi + 3072\,\pi^{10} r^2 x^2 \psi + 11\,\pi^2 r^2 \psi^5 \right)}{3 \left(-256\,\pi^8 r^2 \psi^3 + 512\,\pi^8 r x \psi^3 - 256\,\pi^8 x^2 \psi^3 - \psi^7 \right)} - \\
 & \left. \left(16 \times 2^{1/3} \pi^4 \left(6144\,\pi^8 r^6 \psi^6 - 12\,288\,\pi^8 r^5 x \psi^6 + 6144\,\pi^8 r^4 x^2 \psi^6 + 25 r^4 \psi^{10} \right) \right) \right) \Big/ \\
 & \left(3 \left(-256\,\pi^8 r^2 \psi^3 + 512\,\pi^8 r x \psi^3 - 256\,\pi^8 x^2 \psi^3 - \psi^7 \right) \right. \\
 & \left. \left(-452\,984\,832\,\pi^{22} r^{10} \psi^7 + 1\,811\,939\,328\,\pi^{22} r^9 x \psi^7 - 2\,717\,908\,992\,\pi^{22} r^8 x^2 \right. \right. \\
 & \psi^7 + 1\,811\,939\,328\,\pi^{22} r^7 x^3 \psi^7 - 452\,984\,832\,\pi^{22} r^6 x^4 \psi^7 - 5\,898\,240\,\pi^{14} \\
 & r^8 \psi^{11} + 11\,796\,480\,\pi^{14} r^7 x \psi^{11} - 5\,898\,240\,\pi^{14} r^6 x^2 \psi^{11} - 16\,000\,\pi^6 r^6 \\
 & \left. \left. \psi^{15} + \sqrt{ \left(205\,195\,258\,022\,068\,224\,\pi^{44} r^{20} \psi^{14} - 1\,641\,562\,064\,176\,545\,792 \right. \right. \right.
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \pi^{44} r^{19} x \psi^{14} + 5\,745\,467\,224\,617\,910\,272 \pi^{44} r^{18} x^2 \psi^{14} - \\
& 11\,490\,934\,449\,235\,820\,544 \pi^{44} r^{17} x^3 \psi^{14} + 14\,363\,668\,061\,544\,775\,680 \\
& \pi^{44} r^{16} x^4 \psi^{14} - 11\,490\,934\,449\,235\,820\,544 \pi^{44} r^{15} x^5 \psi^{14} + \\
& 5\,745\,467\,224\,617\,910\,272 \pi^{44} r^{14} x^6 \psi^{14} - 1\,641\,562\,064\,176\,545\,792 \\
& \pi^{44} r^{13} x^7 \psi^{14} + 205\,195\,258\,022\,068\,224 \pi^{44} r^{12} x^8 \psi^{14} + \\
& 1\,543\,714\,325\,397\,504 \pi^{36} r^{18} \psi^{18} - 9\,262\,285\,952\,385\,024 \pi^{36} r^{17} x \psi^{18} + \\
& 23\,155\,714\,880\,962\,560 \pi^{36} r^{16} x^2 \psi^{18} - 30\,874\,286\,507\,950\,080 \pi^{36} r^{15} x^3 \psi^{18} + \\
& 23\,155\,714\,880\,962\,560 \pi^{36} r^{14} x^4 \psi^{18} - 9\,262\,285\,952\,385\,024 \pi^{36} r^{13} x^5 \psi^{18} + \\
& 1\,543\,714\,325\,397\,504 \pi^{36} r^{12} x^6 \psi^{18} + 2\,899\,102\,924\,800 \pi^{28} r^{16} \psi^{22} - \\
& 11\,596\,411\,699\,200 \pi^{28} r^{15} x \psi^{22} + 17\,394\,617\,548\,800 \pi^{28} r^{14} x^2 \psi^{22} - \\
& 11\,596\,411\,699\,200 \pi^{28} r^{13} x^3 \psi^{22} + 2\,899\,102\,924\,800 \pi^{28} r^{12} x^4 \psi^{22})^{1/3} - \\
& \left(-452\,984\,832 \pi^{22} r^{10} \psi^7 + 1\,811\,939\,328 \pi^{22} r^9 x \psi^7 - 2\,717\,908\,992 \pi^{22} r^8 x^2 \psi^7 + \right. \\
& 1\,811\,939\,328 \pi^{22} r^7 x^3 \psi^7 - 452\,984\,832 \pi^{22} r^6 x^4 \psi^7 - 5\,898\,240 \pi^{14} r^8 \psi^{11} + \\
& 11\,796\,480 \pi^{14} r^7 x \psi^{11} - 5\,898\,240 \pi^{14} r^6 x^2 \psi^{11} - 16\,000 \pi^6 r^6 \psi^{15} + \\
& \left. \sqrt{ (205\,195\,258\,022\,068\,224 \pi^{44} r^{20} \psi^{14} - 1\,641\,562\,064\,176\,545\,792 \pi^{44} r^{19} x \psi^{14} + \right. \\
& 5\,745\,467\,224\,617\,910\,272 \pi^{44} r^{18} x^2 \psi^{14} - 11\,490\,934\,449\,235\,820\,544 \pi^{44} r^{17} x^3 \\
& \psi^{14} + 14\,363\,668\,061\,544\,775\,680 \pi^{44} r^{16} x^4 \psi^{14} - 11\,490\,934\,449\,235\,820\,544 \\
& \pi^{44} r^{15} x^5 \psi^{14} + 5\,745\,467\,224\,617\,910\,272 \pi^{44} r^{14} x^6 \psi^{14} - \\
& 1\,641\,562\,064\,176\,545\,792 \pi^{44} r^{13} x^7 \psi^{14} + 205\,195\,258\,022\,068\,224 \pi^{44} r^{12} \\
& x^8 \psi^{14} + 1\,543\,714\,325\,397\,504 \pi^{36} r^{18} \psi^{18} - 9\,262\,285\,952\,385\,024 \pi^{36} r^{17} x \psi^{18} + \\
& 23\,155\,714\,880\,962\,560 \pi^{36} r^{16} x^2 \psi^{18} - 30\,874\,286\,507\,950\,080 \pi^{36} r^{15} x^3 \psi^{18} + \\
& 23\,155\,714\,880\,962\,560 \pi^{36} r^{14} x^4 \psi^{18} - 9\,262\,285\,952\,385\,024 \pi^{36} r^{13} x^5 \psi^{18} + \\
& 1\,543\,714\,325\,397\,504 \pi^{36} r^{12} x^6 \psi^{18} + 2\,899\,102\,924\,800 \pi^{28} r^{16} \psi^{22} - \\
& 11\,596\,411\,699\,200 \pi^{28} r^{15} x \psi^{22} + 17\,394\,617\,548\,800 \pi^{28} r^{14} x^2 \psi^{22} - \\
& 11\,596\,411\,699\,200 \pi^{28} r^{13} x^3 \psi^{22} + 2\,899\,102\,924\,800 \pi^{28} r^{12} x^4 \psi^{22})^{1/3} / \\
& \left(3 \times 2^{1/3} \left(-256 \pi^8 r^2 \psi^3 + 512 \pi^8 r x \psi^3 - 256 \pi^8 x^2 \psi^3 - \psi^7 \right) \right) + \\
& \left(\frac{1728 \pi^3 r^3}{\psi^3} - \frac{192 \pi r \left(3072 \pi^{10} r^4 - 6144 \pi^{10} r^3 x + 3072 \pi^{10} r^2 x^2 + 11 \pi^2 r^2 \psi^4 \right)}{\psi^3 \left(256 \pi^8 r^2 - 512 \pi^8 r x + 256 \pi^8 x^2 + \psi^4 \right)} + \right. \\
& \left. \frac{128 \left(1024 \pi^{11} r^5 - 2048 \pi^{11} r^4 x + 1024 \pi^{11} r^3 x^2 + 3 \pi^3 r^3 \psi^4 \right)}{\psi^3 \left(256 \pi^8 r^2 - 512 \pi^8 r x + 256 \pi^8 x^2 + \psi^4 \right)} \right) / \\
& \left(4 \sqrt{ \left(\frac{36 \pi^2 r^2}{\psi^2} - \frac{4 \left(3072 \pi^{10} r^4 - 6144 \pi^{10} r^3 x + 3072 \pi^{10} r^2 x^2 + 11 \pi^2 r^2 \psi^4 \right)}{\psi^2 \left(256 \pi^8 r^2 - 512 \pi^8 r x + 256 \pi^8 x^2 + \psi^4 \right)} - \right. \right. \\
& \left. \left(4 \left(3072 \pi^{10} r^4 \psi - 6144 \pi^{10} r^3 x \psi + 3072 \pi^{10} r^2 x^2 \psi + 11 \pi^2 r^2 \psi^5 \right) \right) / \right. \\
& \left. \left(3 \left(-256 \pi^8 r^2 \psi^3 + 512 \pi^8 r x \psi^3 - 256 \pi^8 x^2 \psi^3 - \psi^7 \right) \right) + \right. \\
& \left. \left(16 \times 2^{1/3} \pi^4 \left(6144 \pi^8 r^6 \psi^6 - 12\,288 \pi^8 r^5 x \psi^6 + 6144 \pi^8 r^4 x^2 \psi^6 + 25 r^4 \psi^{10} \right) \right) / \right. \\
& \left. \left(3 \left(-256 \pi^8 r^2 \psi^3 + 512 \pi^8 r x \psi^3 - 256 \pi^8 x^2 \psi^3 - \psi^7 \right) \right) \right. \\
& \left. \left(-452\,984\,832 \pi^{22} r^{10} \psi^7 + 1\,811\,939\,328 \pi^{22} r^9 x \psi^7 - 2\,717\,908\,992 \pi^{22} \right. \right.
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& r^8 x^2 \psi^7 + 1811939328 \pi^{22} r^7 x^3 \psi^7 - 452984832 \pi^{22} r^6 x^4 \psi^7 - \\
& 5898240 \pi^{14} r^8 \psi^{11} + 11796480 \pi^{14} r^7 x \psi^{11} - 5898240 \pi^{14} r^6 x^2 \psi^{11} - \\
& 16000 \pi^6 r^6 \psi^{15} + \sqrt{\left(205195258022068224 \pi^{44} r^{20} \psi^{14} - \right. \\
& \quad 1641562064176545792 \pi^{44} r^{19} x \psi^{14} + 5745467224617910272 \\
& \quad \pi^{44} r^{18} x^2 \psi^{14} - 11490934449235820544 \pi^{44} r^{17} \\
& \quad x^3 \psi^{14} + 14363668061544775680 \pi^{44} r^{16} x^4 \psi^{14} - \\
& \quad 11490934449235820544 \pi^{44} r^{15} x^5 \psi^{14} + 5745467224617910272 \\
& \quad \pi^{44} r^{14} x^6 \psi^{14} - 1641562064176545792 \pi^{44} r^{13} x^7 \psi^{14} + \\
& \quad 205195258022068224 \pi^{44} r^{12} x^8 \psi^{14} + 1543714325397504 \pi^{36} r^{18} \\
& \quad \psi^{18} - 9262285952385024 \pi^{36} r^{17} x \psi^{18} + 23155714880962560 \\
& \quad \pi^{36} r^{16} x^2 \psi^{18} - 30874286507950080 \pi^{36} r^{15} x^3 \psi^{18} + \\
& \quad 23155714880962560 \pi^{36} r^{14} x^4 \psi^{18} - 9262285952385024 \\
& \quad \pi^{36} r^{13} x^5 \psi^{18} + 1543714325397504 \pi^{36} r^{12} x^6 \psi^{18} + \\
& \quad 2899102924800 \pi^{28} r^{16} \psi^{22} - 11596411699200 \pi^{28} r^{15} x \psi^{22} + \\
& \quad 17394617548800 \pi^{28} r^{14} x^2 \psi^{22} - 11596411699200 \\
& \quad \left. \left. \left. \left. \left. \pi^{28} r^{13} x^3 \psi^{22} + 2899102924800 \pi^{28} r^{12} x^4 \psi^{22} \right) \right) \right)^{1/3} \right\} + \\
& \left(-452984832 \pi^{22} r^{10} \psi^7 + 1811939328 \pi^{22} r^9 x \psi^7 - 2717908992 \right. \\
& \quad \pi^{22} r^8 x^2 \psi^7 + 1811939328 \pi^{22} r^7 x^3 \psi^7 - 452984832 \pi^{22} r^6 x^4 \psi^7 - \\
& \quad 5898240 \pi^{14} r^8 \psi^{11} + 11796480 \pi^{14} r^7 x \psi^{11} - 5898240 \pi^{14} r^6 x^2 \psi^{11} - \\
& \quad 16000 \pi^6 r^6 \psi^{15} + \sqrt{\left(205195258022068224 \pi^{44} r^{20} \psi^{14} - \right. \\
& \quad 1641562064176545792 \pi^{44} r^{19} x \psi^{14} + 5745467224617910272 \\
& \quad \pi^{44} r^{18} x^2 \psi^{14} - 11490934449235820544 \pi^{44} r^{17} x^3 \psi^{14} + \\
& \quad 14363668061544775680 \pi^{44} r^{16} x^4 \psi^{14} - 11490934449235820544 \\
& \quad \pi^{44} r^{15} x^5 \psi^{14} + 5745467224617910272 \pi^{44} r^{14} x^6 \psi^{14} - \\
& \quad 1641562064176545792 \pi^{44} r^{13} x^7 \psi^{14} + 205195258022068224 \pi^{44} \\
& \quad r^{12} x^8 \psi^{14} + 1543714325397504 \pi^{36} r^{18} \psi^{18} - 9262285952385024 \\
& \quad \pi^{36} r^{17} x \psi^{18} + 23155714880962560 \pi^{36} r^{16} x^2 \psi^{18} - \\
& \quad 30874286507950080 \pi^{36} r^{15} x^3 \psi^{18} + 23155714880962560 \pi^{36} r^{14} \\
& \quad x^4 \psi^{18} - 9262285952385024 \pi^{36} r^{13} x^5 \psi^{18} + 1543714325397504 \\
& \quad \pi^{36} r^{12} x^6 \psi^{18} + 2899102924800 \pi^{28} r^{16} \psi^{22} - 11596411699200 \\
& \quad \pi^{28} r^{15} x \psi^{22} + 17394617548800 \pi^{28} r^{14} x^2 \psi^{22} - 11596411699200 \\
& \quad \left. \left. \left. \left. \left. \pi^{28} r^{13} x^3 \psi^{22} + 2899102924800 \pi^{28} r^{12} x^4 \psi^{22} \right) \right) \right)^{1/3} \right\} / \\
& \left(3 \times 2^{1/3} \left(-256 \pi^8 r^2 \psi^3 + 512 \pi^8 r x \psi^3 - 256 \pi^8 x^2 \psi^3 - \psi^7 \right) \right) \left. \left. \left. \left. \left. \right) \right) \right) \right\}, \\
& \left\{ j \rightarrow \frac{3 \pi r}{\psi} + \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{\left(\frac{36 \pi^2 r^2}{\psi^2} - \frac{4 \left(3072 \pi^{10} r^4 - 6144 \pi^{10} r^3 x + 3072 \pi^{10} r^2 x^2 + 11 \pi^2 r^2 \psi^4 \right)}{\psi^2 \left(256 \pi^8 r^2 - 512 \pi^8 r x + 256 \pi^8 x^2 + \psi^4 \right)} \right) - \right.} \\
& \left. \frac{4 \left(3072 \pi^{10} r^4 \psi - 6144 \pi^{10} r^3 x \psi + 3072 \pi^{10} r^2 x^2 \psi + 11 \pi^2 r^2 \psi^5 \right)}{3 \left(-256 \pi^8 r^2 \psi^3 + 512 \pi^8 r x \psi^3 - 256 \pi^8 x^2 \psi^3 - \psi^7 \right)} + \right.
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & (16 \times 2^{1/3} \pi^4 \\
 & \quad (6144 \pi^8 r^6 \psi^6 - 12\,288 \pi^8 r^5 x \psi^6 + 6144 \pi^8 r^4 x^2 \psi^6 + 25 r^4 \psi^{10}) \Big/ \\
 & \quad \left(3 (-256 \pi^8 r^2 \psi^3 + 512 \pi^8 r x \psi^3 - 256 \pi^8 x^2 \psi^3 - \psi^7) \right. \\
 & \quad \left(-452\,984\,832 \pi^{22} r^{10} \psi^7 + 1\,811\,939\,328 \pi^{22} r^9 x \psi^7 - 2\,717\,908\,992 \pi^{22} r^8 x^2 \psi^7 \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \psi^7 + 1\,811\,939\,328 \pi^{22} r^7 x^3 \psi^7 - 452\,984\,832 \pi^{22} r^6 x^4 \psi^7 - 5\,898\,240 \pi^{14} r^8 \psi^{11} + 11\,796\,480 \pi^{14} r^7 x \psi^{11} - 5\,898\,240 \pi^{14} r^6 x^2 \psi^{11} - 16\,000 \pi^6 r^6 \psi^{15} \right. \\
 & \quad \left. + \sqrt{(205\,195\,258\,022\,068\,224 \pi^{44} r^{20} \psi^{14} - 1\,641\,562\,064\,176\,545\,792 \pi^{44} r^{19} x \psi^{14} - 5\,745\,467\,224\,617\,910\,272 \pi^{44} r^{18} x^2 \psi^{14} - 11\,490\,934\,449\,235\,820\,544 \pi^{44} r^{17} x^3 \psi^{14} + 14\,363\,668\,061\,544\,775\,680 \pi^{44} r^{16} x^4 \psi^{14} - 11\,490\,934\,449\,235\,820\,544 \pi^{44} r^{15} x^5 \psi^{14} + 5\,745\,467\,224\,617\,910\,272 \pi^{44} r^{14} x^6 \psi^{14} - 1\,641\,562\,064\,176\,545\,792 \pi^{44} r^{13} x^7 \psi^{14} + 205\,195\,258\,022\,068\,224 \pi^{44} r^{12} x^8 \psi^{14} + 1\,543\,714\,325\,397\,504 \pi^{36} r^{18} \psi^{18} - 9\,262\,285\,952\,385\,024 \pi^{36} r^{17} x \psi^{18} + 23\,155\,714\,880\,962\,560 \pi^{36} r^{16} x^2 \psi^{18} - 30\,874\,286\,507\,950\,080 \pi^{36} r^{15} x^3 \psi^{18} + 23\,155\,714\,880\,962\,560 \pi^{36} r^{14} x^4 \psi^{18} - 9\,262\,285\,952\,385\,024 \pi^{36} r^{13} x^5 \psi^{18} + 1\,543\,714\,325\,397\,504 \pi^{36} r^{12} x^6 \psi^{18} + 2\,899\,102\,924\,800 \pi^{28} r^{16} \psi^{22} - 11\,596\,411\,699\,200 \pi^{28} r^{15} x \psi^{22} + 17\,394\,617\,548\,800 \pi^{28} r^{14} x^2 \psi^{22} - 11\,596\,411\,699\,200 \pi^{28} r^{13} x^3 \psi^{22} + 2\,899\,102\,924\,800 \pi^{28} r^{12} x^4 \psi^{22}) \Big)^{1/3} \right) + \\
 & \quad \left(-452\,984\,832 \pi^{22} r^{10} \psi^7 + 1\,811\,939\,328 \pi^{22} r^9 x \psi^7 - 2\,717\,908\,992 \pi^{22} r^8 x^2 \psi^7 + 1\,811\,939\,328 \pi^{22} r^7 x^3 \psi^7 - 452\,984\,832 \pi^{22} r^6 x^4 \psi^7 - 5\,898\,240 \pi^{14} r^8 \psi^{11} + 11\,796\,480 \pi^{14} r^7 x \psi^{11} - 5\,898\,240 \pi^{14} r^6 x^2 \psi^{11} - 16\,000 \pi^6 r^6 \psi^{15} + \sqrt{(205\,195\,258\,022\,068\,224 \pi^{44} r^{20} \psi^{14} - 1\,641\,562\,064\,176\,545\,792 \pi^{44} r^{19} x \psi^{14} + 5\,745\,467\,224\,617\,910\,272 \pi^{44} r^{18} x^2 \psi^{14} - 11\,490\,934\,449\,235\,820\,544 \pi^{44} r^{17} x^3 \psi^{14} + 14\,363\,668\,061\,544\,775\,680 \pi^{44} r^{16} x^4 \psi^{14} - 11\,490\,934\,449\,235\,820\,544 \pi^{44} r^{15} x^5 \psi^{14} + 5\,745\,467\,224\,617\,910\,272 \pi^{44} r^{14} x^6 \psi^{14} - 1\,641\,562\,064\,176\,545\,792 \pi^{44} r^{13} x^7 \psi^{14} + 205\,195\,258\,022\,068\,224 \pi^{44} r^{12} x^8 \psi^{14} + 1\,543\,714\,325\,397\,504 \pi^{36} r^{18} \psi^{18} - 9\,262\,285\,952\,385\,024 \pi^{36} r^{17} x \psi^{18} + 23\,155\,714\,880\,962\,560 \pi^{36} r^{16} x^2 \psi^{18} - 30\,874\,286\,507\,950\,080 \pi^{36} r^{15} x^3 \psi^{18} + 23\,155\,714\,880\,962\,560 \pi^{36} r^{14} x^4 \psi^{18} - 9\,262\,285\,952\,385\,024 \pi^{36} r^{13} x^5 \psi^{18} + 1\,543\,714\,325\,397\,504 \pi^{36} r^{12} x^6 \psi^{18} + 2\,899\,102\,924\,800 \pi^{28} r^{16} \psi^{22} - 11\,596\,411\,699\,200 \pi^{28} r^{15} x \psi^{22} + 17\,394\,617\,548\,800 \pi^{28} r^{14} x^2 \psi^{22} - 11\,596\,411\,699\,200 \pi^{28} r^{13} x^3 \psi^{22} + 2\,899\,102\,924\,800 \pi^{28} r^{12} x^4 \psi^{22}) \Big)^{1/3} \right) / \\
 & \quad \left. \left(3 \times 2^{1/3} (-256 \pi^8 r^2 \psi^3 + 512 \pi^8 r x \psi^3 - 256 \pi^8 x^2 \psi^3 - \psi^7) \right) \right) + \\
 & \quad \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{\left(\frac{72 \pi^2 r^2}{\psi^2} - \frac{4 (3072 \pi^{10} r^4 - 6144 \pi^{10} r^3 x + 3072 \pi^{10} r^2 x^2 + 11 \pi^2 r^2 \psi^4)}{\psi^2 (256 \pi^8 r^2 - 512 \pi^8 r x + 256 \pi^8 x^2 + \psi^4)} \right) + }
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& 4 \left(3072 \pi^{10} r^4 \psi - 6144 \pi^{10} r^3 x \psi + 3072 \pi^{10} r^2 x^2 \psi + 11 \pi^2 r^2 \psi^5 \right) \\
& \quad - \frac{3 \left(-256 \pi^8 r^2 \psi^3 + 512 \pi^8 r x \psi^3 - 256 \pi^8 x^2 \psi^3 - \psi^7 \right)}{16 \times 2^{1/3} \pi^4} \\
& \quad \left(6144 \pi^8 r^6 \psi^6 - 12288 \pi^8 r^5 x \psi^6 + 6144 \pi^8 r^4 x^2 \psi^6 + 25 r^4 \psi^{10} \right) / \\
& \quad \left(3 \left(-256 \pi^8 r^2 \psi^3 + 512 \pi^8 r x \psi^3 - 256 \pi^8 x^2 \psi^3 - \psi^7 \right) \right. \\
& \quad \left(-452984832 \pi^{22} r^{10} \psi^7 + 1811939328 \pi^{22} r^9 x \psi^7 - 2717908992 \pi^{22} r^8 x^2 \right. \\
& \quad \left. \psi^7 + 1811939328 \pi^{22} r^7 x^3 \psi^7 - 452984832 \pi^{22} r^6 x^4 \psi^7 - 5898240 \pi^{14} r^8 \psi^{11} \right. \\
& \quad \left. + 11796480 \pi^{14} r^7 x \psi^{11} - 5898240 \pi^{14} r^6 x^2 \psi^{11} - 16000 \pi^6 r^6 \psi^{15} \right. \\
& \quad \left. + \sqrt{\left(205195258022068224 \pi^{44} r^{20} \psi^{14} - 1641562064176545792 \pi^{44} r^{19} x \psi^{14} \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. + 5745467224617910272 \pi^{44} r^{18} x^2 \psi^{14} - 11490934449235820544 \pi^{44} r^{17} x^3 \psi^{14} \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. + 14363668061544775680 \pi^{44} r^{16} x^4 \psi^{14} - 11490934449235820544 \pi^{44} r^{15} x^5 \psi^{14} \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. + 5745467224617910272 \pi^{44} r^{14} x^6 \psi^{14} - 1641562064176545792 \pi^{44} r^{13} x^7 \psi^{14} \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. + 205195258022068224 \pi^{44} r^{12} x^8 \psi^{14} + 1543714325397504 \pi^{36} r^{18} \psi^{18} - 9262285952385024 \pi^{36} r^{17} x \psi^{18} \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. + 23155714880962560 \pi^{36} r^{16} x^2 \psi^{18} - 30874286507950080 \pi^{36} r^{15} x^3 \psi^{18} \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. + 23155714880962560 \pi^{36} r^{14} x^4 \psi^{18} - 9262285952385024 \pi^{36} r^{13} x^5 \psi^{18} \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. + 1543714325397504 \pi^{36} r^{12} x^6 \psi^{18} + 2899102924800 \pi^{28} r^{16} \psi^{22} - 11596411699200 \pi^{28} r^{15} x \psi^{22} \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. + 17394617548800 \pi^{28} r^{14} x^2 \psi^{22} - 11596411699200 \pi^{28} r^{13} x^3 \psi^{22} \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. + 2899102924800 \pi^{28} r^{12} x^4 \psi^{22} \right) \right)^{1/3} \left. \right) \\
& \quad \left(-452984832 \pi^{22} r^{10} \psi^7 + 1811939328 \pi^{22} r^9 x \psi^7 - 2717908992 \pi^{22} r^8 x^2 \psi^7 + \right. \\
& \quad \left. 1811939328 \pi^{22} r^7 x^3 \psi^7 - 452984832 \pi^{22} r^6 x^4 \psi^7 - 5898240 \pi^{14} r^8 \psi^{11} + \right. \\
& \quad \left. 11796480 \pi^{14} r^7 x \psi^{11} - 5898240 \pi^{14} r^6 x^2 \psi^{11} - 16000 \pi^6 r^6 \psi^{15} + \right. \\
& \quad \left. \sqrt{\left(205195258022068224 \pi^{44} r^{20} \psi^{14} - 1641562064176545792 \pi^{44} r^{19} x \psi^{14} \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. + 5745467224617910272 \pi^{44} r^{18} x^2 \psi^{14} - 11490934449235820544 \pi^{44} r^{17} x^3 \psi^{14} \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. + 14363668061544775680 \pi^{44} r^{16} x^4 \psi^{14} - 11490934449235820544 \pi^{44} r^{15} x^5 \psi^{14} \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. + 5745467224617910272 \pi^{44} r^{14} x^6 \psi^{14} - 1641562064176545792 \pi^{44} r^{13} x^7 \psi^{14} \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. + 205195258022068224 \pi^{44} r^{12} x^8 \psi^{14} + 1543714325397504 \pi^{36} r^{18} \psi^{18} - 9262285952385024 \pi^{36} r^{17} x \psi^{18} \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. + 23155714880962560 \pi^{36} r^{16} x^2 \psi^{18} - 30874286507950080 \pi^{36} r^{15} x^3 \psi^{18} \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. + 23155714880962560 \pi^{36} r^{14} x^4 \psi^{18} - 9262285952385024 \pi^{36} r^{13} x^5 \psi^{18} \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. + 1543714325397504 \pi^{36} r^{12} x^6 \psi^{18} + 2899102924800 \pi^{28} r^{16} \psi^{22} - 11596411699200 \pi^{28} r^{15} x \psi^{22} \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. + 17394617548800 \pi^{28} r^{14} x^2 \psi^{22} - 11596411699200 \pi^{28} r^{13} x^3 \psi^{22} \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. + 2899102924800 \pi^{28} r^{12} x^4 \psi^{22} \right) \right)^{1/3} / \\
& \quad \left(3 \times 2^{1/3} \left(-256 \pi^8 r^2 \psi^3 + 512 \pi^8 r x \psi^3 - 256 \pi^8 x^2 \psi^3 - \psi^7 \right) \right) + \\
& \quad \left(\frac{1728 \pi^3 r^3}{\psi^3} - \frac{192 \pi r \left(3072 \pi^{10} r^4 - 6144 \pi^{10} r^3 x + 3072 \pi^{10} r^2 x^2 + 11 \pi^2 r^2 \psi^4 \right)}{\psi^3 \left(256 \pi^8 r^2 - 512 \pi^8 r x + 256 \pi^8 x^2 + \psi^4 \right)} \right) +
\end{aligned}$$

$$\left(\pi^{36} r^{12} x^6 \psi^{18} + 2899102924800 \pi^{28} r^{16} \psi^{22} - 11596411699200 \pi^{28} r^{15} x \psi^{22} + 17394617548800 \pi^{28} r^{14} x^2 \psi^{22} - 11596411699200 \pi^{28} r^{13} x^3 \psi^{22} + 2899102924800 \pi^{28} r^{12} x^4 \psi^{22} \right)^{1/3} / \left(3 \times 2^{1/3} \left(-256 \pi^8 r^2 \psi^3 + 512 \pi^8 r x \psi^3 - 256 \pi^8 x^2 \psi^3 - \psi^7 \right) \right) \Bigg\} \Bigg\} \Bigg\}$$

Solve[(2 π r - 2 π x) / ((ψ / (2 π)) ^ 2) ==

$$-\frac{(4 j \pi r - 2 j^2 \psi) (4 \pi r \psi - 2 j \psi^2)}{8 \pi (4 j \pi r \psi - j^2 \psi^2)^{3/2}} + \frac{4 \pi r - 4 j \psi}{4 \pi \sqrt{4 j \pi r \psi - j^2 \psi^2}}, r]$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \left\{ r \rightarrow \text{Root} \left[-256 j^4 \pi^8 x^2 \psi^3 - j^4 \psi^7 + (3072 j^3 \pi^9 x^2 \psi^2 + 512 j^4 \pi^8 x \psi^3 + 12 j^3 \pi \psi^6) \#1 + \right. \right. \\ & \quad \left. \left. (-12288 j^2 \pi^{10} x^2 \psi - 6144 j^3 \pi^9 x \psi^2 - 256 j^4 \pi^8 \psi^3 - 44 j^2 \pi^2 \psi^5) \#1^2 + \right. \right. \\ & \quad \left. \left. (16384 j \pi^{11} x^2 + 24576 j^2 \pi^{10} x \psi + 3072 j^3 \pi^9 \psi^2 + 48 j \pi^3 \psi^4) \#1^3 + \right. \right. \\ & \quad \left. \left. (-32768 j \pi^{11} x - 12288 j^2 \pi^{10} \psi - 16 \pi^4 \psi^3) \#1^4 + 16384 j \pi^{11} \#1^5 \&, 1 \right] \right\}, \\ & \left\{ r \rightarrow \text{Root} \left[-256 j^4 \pi^8 x^2 \psi^3 - j^4 \psi^7 + (3072 j^3 \pi^9 x^2 \psi^2 + 512 j^4 \pi^8 x \psi^3 + 12 j^3 \pi \psi^6) \#1 + \right. \right. \\ & \quad \left. \left. (-12288 j^2 \pi^{10} x^2 \psi - 6144 j^3 \pi^9 x \psi^2 - 256 j^4 \pi^8 \psi^3 - 44 j^2 \pi^2 \psi^5) \#1^2 + \right. \right. \\ & \quad \left. \left. (16384 j \pi^{11} x^2 + 24576 j^2 \pi^{10} x \psi + 3072 j^3 \pi^9 \psi^2 + 48 j \pi^3 \psi^4) \#1^3 + \right. \right. \\ & \quad \left. \left. (-32768 j \pi^{11} x - 12288 j^2 \pi^{10} \psi - 16 \pi^4 \psi^3) \#1^4 + 16384 j \pi^{11} \#1^5 \&, 2 \right] \right\}, \\ & \left\{ r \rightarrow \text{Root} \left[-256 j^4 \pi^8 x^2 \psi^3 - j^4 \psi^7 + (3072 j^3 \pi^9 x^2 \psi^2 + 512 j^4 \pi^8 x \psi^3 + 12 j^3 \pi \psi^6) \#1 + \right. \right. \\ & \quad \left. \left. (-12288 j^2 \pi^{10} x^2 \psi - 6144 j^3 \pi^9 x \psi^2 - 256 j^4 \pi^8 \psi^3 - 44 j^2 \pi^2 \psi^5) \#1^2 + \right. \right. \\ & \quad \left. \left. (16384 j \pi^{11} x^2 + 24576 j^2 \pi^{10} x \psi + 3072 j^3 \pi^9 \psi^2 + 48 j \pi^3 \psi^4) \#1^3 + \right. \right. \\ & \quad \left. \left. (-32768 j \pi^{11} x - 12288 j^2 \pi^{10} \psi - 16 \pi^4 \psi^3) \#1^4 + 16384 j \pi^{11} \#1^5 \&, 3 \right] \right\}, \\ & \left\{ r \rightarrow \text{Root} \left[-256 j^4 \pi^8 x^2 \psi^3 - j^4 \psi^7 + (3072 j^3 \pi^9 x^2 \psi^2 + 512 j^4 \pi^8 x \psi^3 + 12 j^3 \pi \psi^6) \#1 + \right. \right. \\ & \quad \left. \left. (-12288 j^2 \pi^{10} x^2 \psi - 6144 j^3 \pi^9 x \psi^2 - 256 j^4 \pi^8 \psi^3 - 44 j^2 \pi^2 \psi^5) \#1^2 + \right. \right. \\ & \quad \left. \left. (16384 j \pi^{11} x^2 + 24576 j^2 \pi^{10} x \psi + 3072 j^3 \pi^9 \psi^2 + 48 j \pi^3 \psi^4) \#1^3 + \right. \right. \\ & \quad \left. \left. (-32768 j \pi^{11} x - 12288 j^2 \pi^{10} \psi - 16 \pi^4 \psi^3) \#1^4 + 16384 j \pi^{11} \#1^5 \&, 4 \right] \right\}, \\ & \left\{ r \rightarrow \text{Root} \left[-256 j^4 \pi^8 x^2 \psi^3 - j^4 \psi^7 + (3072 j^3 \pi^9 x^2 \psi^2 + 512 j^4 \pi^8 x \psi^3 + 12 j^3 \pi \psi^6) \#1 + \right. \right. \\ & \quad \left. \left. (-12288 j^2 \pi^{10} x^2 \psi - 6144 j^3 \pi^9 x \psi^2 - 256 j^4 \pi^8 \psi^3 - 44 j^2 \pi^2 \psi^5) \#1^2 + \right. \right. \\ & \quad \left. \left. (16384 j \pi^{11} x^2 + 24576 j^2 \pi^{10} x \psi + 3072 j^3 \pi^9 \psi^2 + 48 j \pi^3 \psi^4) \#1^3 + \right. \right. \\ & \quad \left. \left. (-32768 j \pi^{11} x - 12288 j^2 \pi^{10} \psi - 16 \pi^4 \psi^3) \#1^4 + 16384 j \pi^{11} \#1^5 \&, 5 \right] \right\} \end{aligned}$$

Manipulate[

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Plot3D[{Root[-256 j^4 π^8 x^2 ψ^3 - j^4 ψ^7 + (3072 j^3 π^9 x^2 ψ^2 + 512 j^4 π^8 x ψ^3 + 12 j^3 π ψ^6) #1 +
(-12 288 j^2 π^10 x^2 ψ - 6144 j^3 π^9 x ψ^2 - 256 j^4 π^8 ψ^3 - 44 j^2 π^2 ψ^5) #1^2 +
(16 384 j π^11 x^2 + 24 576 j^2 π^10 x ψ + 3072 j^3 π^9 ψ^2 + 48 j π^3 ψ^4) #1^3 +
(-32 768 j π^11 x - 12 288 j^2 π^10 ψ - 16 π^4 ψ^3) #1^4 + 16 384 j π^11 #1^5 &, 1],
Root[-256 j^4 π^8 x^2 ψ^3 - j^4 ψ^7 + (3072 j^3 π^9 x^2 ψ^2 + 512 j^4 π^8 x ψ^3 + 12 j^3 π ψ^6) #1 +
(-12 288 j^2 π^10 x^2 ψ - 6144 j^3 π^9 x ψ^2 - 256 j^4 π^8 ψ^3 - 44 j^2 π^2 ψ^5) #1^2 +
(16 384 j π^11 x^2 + 24 576 j^2 π^10 x ψ + 3072 j^3 π^9 ψ^2 + 48 j π^3 ψ^4) #1^3 +
(-32 768 j π^11 x - 12 288 j^2 π^10 ψ - 16 π^4 ψ^3) #1^4 + 16 384 j π^11 #1^5 &, 2],
Root[-256 j^4 π^8 x^2 ψ^3 - j^4 ψ^7 + (3072 j^3 π^9 x^2 ψ^2 + 512 j^4 π^8 x ψ^3 + 12 j^3 π ψ^6) #1 +
(-12 288 j^2 π^10 x^2 ψ - 6144 j^3 π^9 x ψ^2 - 256 j^4 π^8 ψ^3 - 44 j^2 π^2 ψ^5) #1^2 +
(16 384 j π^11 x^2 + 24 576 j^2 π^10 x ψ + 3072 j^3 π^9 ψ^2 + 48 j π^3 ψ^4) #1^3 +
(-32 768 j π^11 x - 12 288 j^2 π^10 ψ - 16 π^4 ψ^3) #1^4 + 16 384 j π^11 #1^5 &, 3],
Root[-256 j^4 π^8 x^2 ψ^3 - j^4 ψ^7 + (3072 j^3 π^9 x^2 ψ^2 + 512 j^4 π^8 x ψ^3 + 12 j^3 π ψ^6) #1 +
(-12 288 j^2 π^10 x^2 ψ - 6144 j^3 π^9 x ψ^2 - 256 j^4 π^8 ψ^3 - 44 j^2 π^2 ψ^5) #1^2 +
(16 384 j π^11 x^2 + 24 576 j^2 π^10 x ψ + 3072 j^3 π^9 ψ^2 + 48 j π^3 ψ^4) #1^3 +
(-32 768 j π^11 x - 12 288 j^2 π^10 ψ - 16 π^4 ψ^3) #1^4 + 16 384 j π^11 #1^5 &, 4],
Root[-256 j^4 π^8 x^2 ψ^3 - j^4 ψ^7 + (3072 j^3 π^9 x^2 ψ^2 + 512 j^4 π^8 x ψ^3 + 12 j^3 π ψ^6) #1 +
(-12 288 j^2 π^10 x^2 ψ - 6144 j^3 π^9 x ψ^2 - 256 j^4 π^8 ψ^3 - 44 j^2 π^2 ψ^5) #1^2 +
(16 384 j π^11 x^2 + 24 576 j^2 π^10 x ψ + 3072 j^3 π^9 ψ^2 + 48 j π^3 ψ^4) #1^3 +
(-32 768 j π^11 x - 12 288 j^2 π^10 ψ - 16 π^4 ψ^3) #1^4 + 16 384 j π^11 #1^5 &, 5]},
{j, -10, 10}, {x, -10, 10}], {ψ, -2 π, 2 π}]

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Manipulate[SphericalPlot3D[
  {Root[-256 j^4 π^8 x^2 ψ^3 - j^4 ψ^7 + (3072 j^3 π^9 x^2 ψ^2 + 512 j^4 π^8 x ψ^3 + 12 j^3 π ψ^6) #1 +
    (-12 288 j^2 π^10 x^2 ψ - 6144 j^3 π^9 x ψ^2 - 256 j^4 π^8 ψ^3 - 44 j^2 π^2 ψ^5) #1^2 +
    (16 384 j π^11 x^2 + 24 576 j^2 π^10 x ψ + 3072 j^3 π^9 ψ^2 + 48 j π^3 ψ^4) #1^3 +
    (-32 768 j π^11 x - 12 288 j^2 π^10 ψ - 16 π^4 ψ^3) #1^4 + 16 384 j π^11 #1^5 &, 1],
  Root[-256 j^4 π^8 x^2 ψ^3 - j^4 ψ^7 + (3072 j^3 π^9 x^2 ψ^2 + 512 j^4 π^8 x ψ^3 + 12 j^3 π ψ^6) #1 +
    (-12 288 j^2 π^10 x^2 ψ - 6144 j^3 π^9 x ψ^2 - 256 j^4 π^8 ψ^3 - 44 j^2 π^2 ψ^5) #1^2 +
    (16 384 j π^11 x^2 + 24 576 j^2 π^10 x ψ + 3072 j^3 π^9 ψ^2 + 48 j π^3 ψ^4) #1^3 +
    (-32 768 j π^11 x - 12 288 j^2 π^10 ψ - 16 π^4 ψ^3) #1^4 + 16 384 j π^11 #1^5 &, 2],
  Root[-256 j^4 π^8 x^2 ψ^3 - j^4 ψ^7 + (3072 j^3 π^9 x^2 ψ^2 + 512 j^4 π^8 x ψ^3 + 12 j^3 π ψ^6) #1 +
    (-12 288 j^2 π^10 x^2 ψ - 6144 j^3 π^9 x ψ^2 - 256 j^4 π^8 ψ^3 - 44 j^2 π^2 ψ^5) #1^2 +
    (16 384 j π^11 x^2 + 24 576 j^2 π^10 x ψ + 3072 j^3 π^9 ψ^2 + 48 j π^3 ψ^4) #1^3 +
    (-32 768 j π^11 x - 12 288 j^2 π^10 ψ - 16 π^4 ψ^3) #1^4 + 16 384 j π^11 #1^5 &, 3],
  Root[-256 j^4 π^8 x^2 ψ^3 - j^4 ψ^7 + (3072 j^3 π^9 x^2 ψ^2 + 512 j^4 π^8 x ψ^3 + 12 j^3 π ψ^6) #1 +
    (-12 288 j^2 π^10 x^2 ψ - 6144 j^3 π^9 x ψ^2 - 256 j^4 π^8 ψ^3 - 44 j^2 π^2 ψ^5) #1^2 +
    (16 384 j π^11 x^2 + 24 576 j^2 π^10 x ψ + 3072 j^3 π^9 ψ^2 + 48 j π^3 ψ^4) #1^3 +
    (-32 768 j π^11 x - 12 288 j^2 π^10 ψ - 16 π^4 ψ^3) #1^4 + 16 384 j π^11 #1^5 &, 4],
  Root[-256 j^4 π^8 x^2 ψ^3 - j^4 ψ^7 + (3072 j^3 π^9 x^2 ψ^2 + 512 j^4 π^8 x ψ^3 + 12 j^3 π ψ^6) #1 +
    (-12 288 j^2 π^10 x^2 ψ - 6144 j^3 π^9 x ψ^2 - 256 j^4 π^8 ψ^3 - 44 j^2 π^2 ψ^5) #1^2 +
    (16 384 j π^11 x^2 + 24 576 j^2 π^10 x ψ + 3072 j^3 π^9 ψ^2 + 48 j π^3 ψ^4) #1^3 +
    (-32 768 j π^11 x - 12 288 j^2 π^10 ψ - 16 π^4 ψ^3) #1^4 + 16 384 j π^11 #1^5 &, 5]},
  {j, -1, 1}, {x, -1, 1}], {ψ, -2 π, 2 π}]

```


$$\text{Solve}\left[\frac{(2\pi r - 2\pi x)}{((\psi / (2\pi))^2)} = -\frac{(4j\pi r - 2j^2\psi)(4\pi r\psi - 2j\psi^2)}{8\pi(4j\pi r\psi - j^2\psi^2)^{3/2}} + \frac{4\pi r - 4j\psi}{4\pi\sqrt{4j\pi r\psi - j^2\psi^2}}, \psi\right]$$

$\{\psi \rightarrow \text{Root}[-16384j\pi^{11}r^5 + 32768j\pi^{11}r^4x - 16384j\pi^{11}r^3x^2 + (12288j^2\pi^{10}r^4 - 24576j^2\pi^{10}r^3x + 12288j^2\pi^{10}r^2x^2)\#1 + (-3072j^3\pi^9r^3 + 6144j^3\pi^9r^2x - 3072j^3\pi^9rx^2)\#1^2 + (256j^4\pi^8r^2 + 16\pi^4r^4 - 512j^4\pi^8rx + 256j^4\pi^8x^2)\#1^3 - 48j\pi^3r^3\#1^4 + 44j^2\pi^2r^2\#1^5 - 12j^3\pi r\#1^6 + j^4\#1^7 \&, 1]\}$,
 $\{\psi \rightarrow \text{Root}[-16384j\pi^{11}r^5 + 32768j\pi^{11}r^4x - 16384j\pi^{11}r^3x^2 + (12288j^2\pi^{10}r^4 - 24576j^2\pi^{10}r^3x + 12288j^2\pi^{10}r^2x^2)\#1 + (-3072j^3\pi^9r^3 + 6144j^3\pi^9r^2x - 3072j^3\pi^9rx^2)\#1^2 + (256j^4\pi^8r^2 + 16\pi^4r^4 - 512j^4\pi^8rx + 256j^4\pi^8x^2)\#1^3 - 48j\pi^3r^3\#1^4 + 44j^2\pi^2r^2\#1^5 - 12j^3\pi r\#1^6 + j^4\#1^7 \&, 2]\}$,
 $\{\psi \rightarrow \text{Root}[-16384j\pi^{11}r^5 + 32768j\pi^{11}r^4x - 16384j\pi^{11}r^3x^2 + (12288j^2\pi^{10}r^4 - 24576j^2\pi^{10}r^3x + 12288j^2\pi^{10}r^2x^2)\#1 + (-3072j^3\pi^9r^3 + 6144j^3\pi^9r^2x - 3072j^3\pi^9rx^2)\#1^2 + (256j^4\pi^8r^2 + 16\pi^4r^4 - 512j^4\pi^8rx + 256j^4\pi^8x^2)\#1^3 - 48j\pi^3r^3\#1^4 + 44j^2\pi^2r^2\#1^5 - 12j^3\pi r\#1^6 + j^4\#1^7 \&, 3]\}$,
 $\{\psi \rightarrow \text{Root}[-16384j\pi^{11}r^5 + 32768j\pi^{11}r^4x - 16384j\pi^{11}r^3x^2 + (12288j^2\pi^{10}r^4 - 24576j^2\pi^{10}r^3x + 12288j^2\pi^{10}r^2x^2)\#1 + (-3072j^3\pi^9r^3 + 6144j^3\pi^9r^2x - 3072j^3\pi^9rx^2)\#1^2 + (256j^4\pi^8r^2 + 16\pi^4r^4 - 512j^4\pi^8rx + 256j^4\pi^8x^2)\#1^3 - 48j\pi^3r^3\#1^4 + 44j^2\pi^2r^2\#1^5 - 12j^3\pi r\#1^6 + j^4\#1^7 \&, 4]\}$,
 $\{\psi \rightarrow \text{Root}[-16384j\pi^{11}r^5 + 32768j\pi^{11}r^4x - 16384j\pi^{11}r^3x^2 + (12288j^2\pi^{10}r^4 - 24576j^2\pi^{10}r^3x + 12288j^2\pi^{10}r^2x^2)\#1 + (-3072j^3\pi^9r^3 + 6144j^3\pi^9r^2x - 3072j^3\pi^9rx^2)\#1^2 + (256j^4\pi^8r^2 + 16\pi^4r^4 - 512j^4\pi^8rx + 256j^4\pi^8x^2)\#1^3 - 48j\pi^3r^3\#1^4 + 44j^2\pi^2r^2\#1^5 - 12j^3\pi r\#1^6 + j^4\#1^7 \&, 5]\}$,
 $\{\psi \rightarrow \text{Root}[-16384j\pi^{11}r^5 + 32768j\pi^{11}r^4x - 16384j\pi^{11}r^3x^2 + (12288j^2\pi^{10}r^4 - 24576j^2\pi^{10}r^3x + 12288j^2\pi^{10}r^2x^2)\#1 + (-3072j^3\pi^9r^3 + 6144j^3\pi^9r^2x - 3072j^3\pi^9rx^2)\#1^2 + (256j^4\pi^8r^2 + 16\pi^4r^4 - 512j^4\pi^8rx + 256j^4\pi^8x^2)\#1^3 - 48j\pi^3r^3\#1^4 + 44j^2\pi^2r^2\#1^5 - 12j^3\pi r\#1^6 + j^4\#1^7 \&, 6]\}$,
 $\{\psi \rightarrow \text{Root}[-16384j\pi^{11}r^5 + 32768j\pi^{11}r^4x - 16384j\pi^{11}r^3x^2 + (12288j^2\pi^{10}r^4 - 24576j^2\pi^{10}r^3x + 12288j^2\pi^{10}r^2x^2)\#1 + (-3072j^3\pi^9r^3 + 6144j^3\pi^9r^2x - 3072j^3\pi^9rx^2)\#1^2 + (256j^4\pi^8r^2 + 16\pi^4r^4 - 512j^4\pi^8rx + 256j^4\pi^8x^2)\#1^3 - 48j\pi^3r^3\#1^4 + 44j^2\pi^2r^2\#1^5 - 12j^3\pi r\#1^6 + j^4\#1^7 \&, 7]\}$

$$\left(2\pi r - 2\pi \sqrt{r^2 - \frac{\sqrt{4j\pi r\psi - j^2\psi^2}}{2\pi}^2} \right) / ((\psi / (2\pi))^2) ==$$

$$- \frac{(4j\pi r - 2j^2\psi)(4\pi r\psi - 2j\psi^2)}{8\pi(4j\pi r\psi - j^2\psi^2)^{3/2}} + \frac{4\pi r - 4j\psi}{4\pi\sqrt{4j\pi r\psi - j^2\psi^2}}$$

$$\frac{4\pi^2 \left(2\pi r - 2\pi \sqrt{r^2 - \frac{4j\pi r\psi - j^2\psi^2}{4\pi^2}} \right)}{\psi^2} == - \frac{(4j\pi r - 2j^2\psi)(4\pi r\psi - 2j\psi^2)}{8\pi(4j\pi r\psi - j^2\psi^2)^{3/2}} + \frac{4\pi r - 4j\psi}{4\pi\sqrt{4j\pi r\psi - j^2\psi^2}}$$

$$(j\psi) / ((\psi / (2\pi))^2)$$

$$\frac{4j\pi^2}{\psi}$$

$$\frac{\sqrt{4j\pi r\psi - j^2\psi^2}}{2\pi}$$

$$D\left[D\left[\frac{\sqrt{4j\pi r\psi - j^2\psi^2}}{2\pi}, j\right], \psi\right]$$

$$- \frac{(4j\pi r - 2j^2\psi)(4\pi r\psi - 2j\psi^2)}{8\pi(4j\pi r\psi - j^2\psi^2)^{3/2}} + \frac{4\pi r - 4j\psi}{4\pi\sqrt{4j\pi r\psi - j^2\psi^2}}$$

$$\text{Solve}[2\pi r - 2\pi \sqrt{r^2 - h^2} == \psi j, j]$$

$$\left\{ \left\{ j \rightarrow -\frac{2(-\pi r + \pi \sqrt{-h^2 + r^2})}{\psi} \right\} \right\}$$

$$\text{Solve}[2\pi r - 2\pi x == \psi j, r]$$

$$\left\{ \left\{ r \rightarrow \frac{2\pi x + j\psi}{2\pi} \right\} \right\}$$

$$\left\{ \left\{ r \rightarrow \frac{4h^2\pi^2 + j^2\psi^2}{4j\pi\psi} \right\} \right\}$$

$$r == \frac{4(r \text{Sin}[\beta])^2\pi^2 + j^2\psi^2}{4j\pi\psi}$$

$$h = \frac{\sqrt{4j\pi r\psi - j^2\psi^2}}{2\pi}$$

$$\text{Solve}\left[\frac{\sqrt{\psi} \sqrt{j} \sqrt{4 \pi r - j^2 \psi^2}}{2 \pi} == r \text{Sin}[\beta], r\right]$$

$$\left\{r \rightarrow \frac{\text{Csc}[\beta]^2 \left(4 j \pi \psi - 4 \sqrt{j^2 \pi^2 \psi^2 - j^3 \pi^2 \psi^3 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}\right)}{8 \pi^2}\right\},$$

$$\left\{r \rightarrow \frac{j \pi \psi \text{Csc}[\beta]^2 + \text{Csc}[\beta]^2 \sqrt{j^2 \pi^2 \psi^2 - j^3 \pi^2 \psi^3 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}}{2 \pi^2}\right\}$$

$$\text{Manipulate}\left[\text{SphericalPlot3D}\left[\frac{j \pi \psi \text{Csc}[\beta]^2 + \text{Csc}[\beta]^2 \sqrt{j^2 \pi^2 \psi^2 - j^3 \pi^2 \psi^3 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}}{2 \pi^2}, \{\beta, -\pi/2, \pi/2\}, \{\psi, -2 \pi, 2 \pi\}\right], \{j, -100, 100}\right]$$

$$\frac{4 (r \operatorname{Sin}[\beta])^2 \pi^2 + j^2 \psi^2}{4 j \pi \psi} == \frac{4 \left(\frac{\sqrt{4 j \pi r \psi - j^2 \psi^2}}{2 \pi} \right)^2 \pi^2 + j^2 \psi^2}{4 j \pi \psi}$$

$$\frac{j^2 \psi^2 + 4 \pi^2 r^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2}{4 j \pi \psi} == r$$

$$\frac{j^2 \psi^2 + 4 \pi^2 r \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2}{4 j \pi \psi} == 1$$

$$\frac{j^2 \psi^2 + 4 \pi^2 r \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2}{4 j \pi \psi} - 1 == 2 \pi r - 2 \pi \sqrt{r^2 - h^2} - \psi j$$

$$-1 + \frac{j^2 \psi^2 + 4 \pi^2 r \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2}{4 j \pi \psi} == 2 \pi r - 2 \pi \sqrt{-h^2 + r^2} - j \psi$$

$$r == \frac{2 \pi \sqrt{r^2 - (r \operatorname{Sin}[\beta])^2} + j \psi}{2 \pi}$$

$$r == \frac{j \psi + 2 \pi \sqrt{r^2 - r^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2}}{2 \pi}$$

$$\text{Solve}\left[r == \frac{j \psi + 2 \pi \sqrt{r^2 - r^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2}}{2 \pi}, r\right]$$

$$\left\{ \left\{ r \rightarrow \frac{\operatorname{Csc}[\beta]^2 \left(4 j \pi \psi - 4 \sqrt{j^2 \pi^2 \psi^2 - j^2 \pi^2 \psi^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2} \right)}{8 \pi^2} \right\}, \right.$$

$$\left. \left\{ r \rightarrow \frac{j \pi \psi \operatorname{Csc}[\beta]^2 + \operatorname{Csc}[\beta]^2 \sqrt{j^2 \pi^2 \psi^2 - j^2 \pi^2 \psi^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2}}{2 \pi^2} \right\} \right\}$$

$$h := r \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]$$

$$r := \frac{2 \pi x + j \psi}{2 \pi}$$

$$x := r$$

$$r := \frac{j \pi \psi \operatorname{Csc}[\beta]^2 + \operatorname{Csc}[\beta]^2 \sqrt{j^2 \pi^2 \psi^2 - j^2 \pi^2 \psi^2 \operatorname{Sin}[\beta]^2}}{2 \pi^2}$$

$$\text{Solve}\left[-1 + \frac{j^2 \psi^2 + 4 \pi^2 r \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{4 j \pi \psi} = 2 \pi r - 2 \pi \sqrt{-(r \text{Sin}[\beta])^2 + r^2} - j \psi, j\right]$$

$$\left\{ \left\{ j \rightarrow \frac{1}{2 (\psi^2 + 4 \pi \psi^2)} \left(4 \pi \psi + 8 \pi^2 r \psi - 8 \pi^2 \psi \sqrt{-r^2 (-1 + \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)} - \sqrt{\left(-16 \pi^2 r (\psi^2 + 4 \pi \psi^2) \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \left(-4 \pi \psi - 8 \pi^2 r \psi + 8 \pi^2 \psi \sqrt{-r^2 (-1 + \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)} \right)^2 \right)} \right) \right\}, \right.$$

$$\left. \left\{ j \rightarrow \frac{1}{2 (\psi^2 + 4 \pi \psi^2)} \left(4 \pi \psi + 8 \pi^2 r \psi - 8 \pi^2 \psi \sqrt{-r^2 (-1 + \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)} + \sqrt{\left(-16 \pi^2 r (\psi^2 + 4 \pi \psi^2) \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \left(-4 \pi \psi - 8 \pi^2 r \psi + 8 \pi^2 \psi \sqrt{-r^2 (-1 + \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)} \right)^2 \right)} \right) \right\} \right\}$$

$$\text{Solve}\left[j = \frac{1}{2 (\psi^2 + 4 \pi \psi^2)} \left(4 \pi \psi + 8 \pi^2 r \psi - 8 \pi^2 \psi \sqrt{-r^2 (-1 + \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)} + \sqrt{\left(-16 \pi^2 r (\psi^2 + 4 \pi \psi^2) \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \left(-4 \pi \psi - 8 \pi^2 r \psi + 8 \pi^2 \psi \sqrt{-r^2 (-1 + \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)} \right)^2 \right)} \right), j\right]$$

$$\text{Solve}\left[-1 + \frac{j^2 \psi^2 + 4 \pi^2 r \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{4 j \pi \psi} = 2 \pi r - 2 \pi \sqrt{-(r \text{Sin}[\beta])^2 + r^2} - j \psi, \psi\right]$$

$$\left\{ \left\{ \psi \rightarrow \frac{1}{2 (j^2 + 4 j^2 \pi)} \left(4 j \pi + 8 j \pi^2 r - 8 j \pi^2 \sqrt{-r^2 (-1 + \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)} - \sqrt{\left(-16 \pi^2 (j^2 + 4 j^2 \pi) r \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \left(-4 j \pi - 8 j \pi^2 r + 8 j \pi^2 \sqrt{-r^2 (-1 + \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)} \right)^2 \right)} \right) \right\}, \right.$$

$$\left. \left\{ \psi \rightarrow \frac{1}{2 (j^2 + 4 j^2 \pi)} \left(4 j \pi + 8 j \pi^2 r - 8 j \pi^2 \sqrt{-r^2 (-1 + \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)} + \sqrt{\left(-16 \pi^2 (j^2 + 4 j^2 \pi) r \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \left(-4 j \pi - 8 j \pi^2 r + 8 j \pi^2 \sqrt{-r^2 (-1 + \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)} \right)^2 \right)} \right) \right\} \right\}$$

ContourPlot3D $\left[\frac{1}{2(j^2 + 4j^2\pi)}\left(4j\pi + 8j\pi^2 r - 8j\pi^2\sqrt{-r^2(-1 + \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)} + \sqrt{\left(-16\pi^2(j^2 + 4j^2\pi)r\text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \left(-4j\pi - 8j\pi^2 r + 8j\pi^2\sqrt{-r^2(-1 + \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)}\right)^2\right)}\right)\right],$
 $\{r, -1, 1\}, \{j, -1, 1\}, \{\beta, -\pi/2, \pi/2\}$

Solve $\left[-1 + \frac{j^2\psi^2 + 4\pi^2 r \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{4j\pi\psi} == 2\pi r - 2\pi\sqrt{-(r\text{Sin}[\beta])^2 + r^2} - j\psi, j\right]$

$\left\{\left\{j \rightarrow \frac{1}{2(\psi^2 + 4\pi\psi^2)}\left(4\pi\psi + 8\pi^2 r\psi - 8\pi^2\psi\sqrt{-r^2(-1 + \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)} - \sqrt{\left(-16\pi^2 r(\psi^2 + 4\pi\psi^2)\text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \left(-4\pi\psi - 8\pi^2 r\psi + 8\pi^2\psi\sqrt{-r^2(-1 + \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)}\right)^2\right)}\right)\right\}\right\},$

$\left\{j \rightarrow \frac{1}{2(\psi^2 + 4\pi\psi^2)}\left(4\pi\psi + 8\pi^2 r\psi - 8\pi^2\psi\sqrt{-r^2(-1 + \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)} + \sqrt{\left(-16\pi^2 r(\psi^2 + 4\pi\psi^2)\text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \left(-4\pi\psi - 8\pi^2 r\psi + 8\pi^2\psi\sqrt{-r^2(-1 + \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)}\right)^2\right)}\right)\right\}$

$$\text{Solve}\left[\mathbf{j} == \frac{1}{2(\psi^2 + 4\pi\psi^2)} \left(4\pi\psi + 8\pi^2 r\psi - 8\pi^2\psi \sqrt{-r^2(-1 + \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)} + \sqrt{\left(-16\pi^2 r(\psi^2 + 4\pi\psi^2) \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \left(-4\pi\psi - 8\pi^2 r\psi + 8\pi^2\psi \sqrt{-r^2(-1 + \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)}\right)^2\right)} \right), r\right]$$

$$\left\{ \left\{ r \rightarrow \left(-8j^2\pi^3\psi^2 + 2j^3\pi^2\psi^3 + 8j^3\pi^3\psi^3 + 4j\pi^3\psi \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - j^2\pi^2\psi^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4j^2\pi^3\psi^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 2\sqrt{\left(16j^4\pi^6\psi^4 - 8j^5\pi^5\psi^5 - 32j^5\pi^6\psi^5 + j^6\pi^4\psi^6 + 8j^6\pi^5\psi^6 + 16j^6\pi^6\psi^6 - 16j^4\pi^6\psi^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8j^5\pi^5\psi^5 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 32j^5\pi^6\psi^5 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - j^6\pi^4\psi^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8j^6\pi^5\psi^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 16j^6\pi^6\psi^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2\right)} \right) / \left(4(-4j\pi^4\psi \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4j^2\pi^4\psi^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \pi^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \right) \right\}, \right.$$

$$\left. \left\{ r \rightarrow \left(-8j^2\pi^3\psi^2 + 2j^3\pi^2\psi^3 + 8j^3\pi^3\psi^3 + 4j\pi^3\psi \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - j^2\pi^2\psi^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 4j^2\pi^3\psi^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 2\sqrt{\left(16j^4\pi^6\psi^4 - 8j^5\pi^5\psi^5 - 32j^5\pi^6\psi^5 + j^6\pi^4\psi^6 + 8j^6\pi^5\psi^6 + 16j^6\pi^6\psi^6 - 16j^4\pi^6\psi^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8j^5\pi^5\psi^5 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 32j^5\pi^6\psi^5 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - j^6\pi^4\psi^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 8j^6\pi^5\psi^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 16j^6\pi^6\psi^6 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2\right)} \right) / \left(4(-4j\pi^4\psi \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 4j^2\pi^4\psi^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \pi^4 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \right) \right\} \right\}$$

$$\text{ContourPlot3D}\left[\frac{1}{2(\psi^2 + 4\pi\psi^2)} \left(4\pi\psi + 8\pi^2 r\psi - 8\pi^2\psi \sqrt{-r^2(-1 + \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)} + \sqrt{\left(-16\pi^2 r(\psi^2 + 4\pi\psi^2) \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \left(-4\pi\psi - 8\pi^2 r\psi + 8\pi^2\psi \sqrt{-r^2(-1 + \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)}\right)^2\right)} \right), \{\psi, -2\pi, 2\pi\}, \{\beta, -\pi/2, \pi/2\}, \{r, -1, 1\}\right]$$


```
Manipulate[SphericalPlot3D[ $\frac{1}{2(\psi^2 + 4\pi\psi^2)} \left( 4\pi\psi + 8\pi^2 r\psi - 8\pi^2\psi \sqrt{-r^2(-1 + \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)} + \sqrt{\left(-16\pi^2 r(\psi^2 + 4\pi\psi^2) \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \left(-4\pi\psi - 8\pi^2 r\psi + 8\pi^2\psi \sqrt{-r^2(-1 + \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)}\right)^2\right)}\right)$ ,
{ $\psi$ , -2 $\pi$ , 2 $\pi$ }, { $\beta$ , - $\pi/2$ ,  $\pi/2$ }, { $r$ , -1, 1}]
```


"beauty.avi"

```
Export["beauty.avi",
```

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Manipulate[SphericalPlot3D[ $\frac{1}{2(\psi^2 + 4\pi\psi^2)} \left( 4\pi\psi + 8\pi^2 r\psi - 8\pi^2\psi \sqrt{-r^2(-1 + \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)} + \sqrt{\left(-16\pi^2 r(\psi^2 + 4\pi\psi^2) \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + \left(-4\pi\psi - 8\pi^2 r\psi + 8\pi^2\psi \sqrt{-r^2(-1 + \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)}\right)^2\right)}\right)$ ,
{ $\psi$ , -2 $\pi$ , 2 $\pi$ }, { $\beta$ , - $\pi/2$ ,  $\pi/2$ }, { $r$ , -1, 1}]]
```

beauty.avi

$$\text{Solve}\left[-1 + \frac{j^2 \psi^2 + 4 \pi^2 r \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{4 j \pi \psi} = 2 \pi r - 2 \pi \sqrt{-h^2 + r^2} - j \psi, \psi\right]$$

$$\left\{ \left\{ \psi \rightarrow \frac{1}{2 (j^2 + 4 j^2 \pi)} \left(4 j \pi + 8 j \pi^2 r - 8 j \pi^2 \sqrt{-h^2 + r^2} - \sqrt{(-4 j \pi - 8 j \pi^2 r + 8 j \pi^2 \sqrt{-h^2 + r^2})^2 - 16 \pi^2 (j^2 + 4 j^2 \pi) r \text{Sin}[\beta]^2} \right) \right\}, \right. \\ \left. \left\{ \psi \rightarrow \frac{1}{2 (j^2 + 4 j^2 \pi)} \left(4 j \pi + 8 j \pi^2 r - 8 j \pi^2 \sqrt{-h^2 + r^2} + \sqrt{(-4 j \pi - 8 j \pi^2 r + 8 j \pi^2 \sqrt{-h^2 + r^2})^2 - 16 \pi^2 (j^2 + 4 j^2 \pi) r \text{Sin}[\beta]^2} \right) \right\} \right\}$$

$$\text{Solve}\left[-1 + \frac{j^2 \psi^2 + 4 \pi^2 r \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{4 j \pi \psi} = 2 \pi r - 2 \pi \sqrt{-h^2 + r^2} - j \psi, r\right]$$

$$\left\{ \left\{ r \rightarrow \left(\text{Csc}[\beta]^2 \right. \right. \right. \\ \left. \left. \left(-j \pi^2 \psi (64 j \pi \psi - 16 j^2 \psi^2 - 64 j^2 \pi \psi^2 - 32 \pi \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8 j \psi \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 32 j \pi \psi \text{Sin}[\beta]^2) - \right. \right. \right. \\ \left. \left. \left. 16 \sqrt{(16 j^4 \pi^6 \psi^4 - 8 j^5 \pi^5 \psi^5 - 32 j^5 \pi^6 \psi^5 + j^6 \pi^4 \psi^6 + 8 j^6 \pi^5 \psi^6 + \right. \right. \right. \\ \left. \left. \left. 16 j^6 \pi^6 \psi^6 + 64 h^2 j^3 \pi^8 \psi^3 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 16 h^2 j^2 \pi^8 \psi^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \right) \right) \right) / \left(2 \pi^4 (-64 j \psi + 16 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2) \right) \right\}, \left\{ r \rightarrow \left(\text{Csc}[\beta]^2 \right. \right. \\ \left. \left. \left(-j \pi^2 \psi (64 j \pi \psi - 16 j^2 \psi^2 - 64 j^2 \pi \psi^2 - 32 \pi \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 8 j \psi \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 + 32 j \pi \psi \text{Sin}[\beta]^2) + \right. \right. \right. \\ \left. \left. \left. 16 \sqrt{(16 j^4 \pi^6 \psi^4 - 8 j^5 \pi^5 \psi^5 - 32 j^5 \pi^6 \psi^5 + j^6 \pi^4 \psi^6 + 8 j^6 \pi^5 \psi^6 + 16 j^6 \pi^6 \psi^6 + 64 h^2 j^3 \right. \right. \right. \\ \left. \left. \left. \pi^8 \psi^3 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 - 16 h^2 j^2 \pi^8 \psi^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^4) \right) \right) \right) / \left(2 \pi^4 (-64 j \psi + 16 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2) \right) \right\} \right\}$$

$$\text{Solve}\left[-1 + \frac{j^2 \psi^2 + 4 \pi^2 r \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{4 j \pi \psi} = 2 \pi r - 2 \pi \sqrt{-h^2 + r^2} - j \psi, j\right]$$

$$\left\{ \left\{ j \rightarrow \frac{1}{2 (\psi^2 + 4 \pi \psi^2)} \left(4 \pi \psi + 8 \pi^2 r \psi - 8 \pi^2 \sqrt{-h^2 + r^2} \psi - \sqrt{(-4 \pi \psi - 8 \pi^2 r \psi + 8 \pi^2 \sqrt{-h^2 + r^2} \psi)^2 - 16 \pi^2 r (\psi^2 + 4 \pi \psi^2) \text{Sin}[\beta]^2} \right) \right\}, \right. \\ \left. \left\{ j \rightarrow \frac{1}{2 (\psi^2 + 4 \pi \psi^2)} \left(4 \pi \psi + 8 \pi^2 r \psi - 8 \pi^2 \sqrt{-h^2 + r^2} \psi + \sqrt{(-4 \pi \psi - 8 \pi^2 r \psi + 8 \pi^2 \sqrt{-h^2 + r^2} \psi)^2 - 16 \pi^2 r (\psi^2 + 4 \pi \psi^2) \text{Sin}[\beta]^2} \right) \right\} \right\}$$

$$\text{Solve}\left[-1 + \frac{j^2 \psi^2 + 4 \pi^2 r \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}{4 j \pi \psi} == 2 \pi r - 2 \pi \sqrt{-h^2 + r^2} - j \psi, \psi\right]$$

$$\left\{\left\{\psi \rightarrow \frac{1}{2 (j^2 + 4 j^2 \pi)} \left(4 j \pi + 8 j \pi^2 r - 8 j \pi^2 \sqrt{-h^2 + r^2} - \sqrt{(-4 j \pi - 8 j \pi^2 r + 8 j \pi^2 \sqrt{-h^2 + r^2})^2 - 16 \pi^2 (j^2 + 4 j^2 \pi) r \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}\right)\right\}, \right. \\ \left. \left\{\psi \rightarrow \frac{1}{2 (j^2 + 4 j^2 \pi)} \left(4 j \pi + 8 j \pi^2 r - 8 j \pi^2 \sqrt{-h^2 + r^2} + \sqrt{(-4 j \pi - 8 j \pi^2 r + 8 j \pi^2 \sqrt{-h^2 + r^2})^2 - 16 \pi^2 (j^2 + 4 j^2 \pi) r \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}\right)\right\}\right\}$$

$$\text{Solve}\left[r == \frac{4 (r \text{Sin}[\beta])^2 \pi^2 + j^2 \psi^2}{4 j \pi \psi}, j\right]$$

$$\left\{\left\{j \rightarrow \frac{2 (\pi r \psi - \sqrt{\pi^2 r^2 \psi^2 - \pi^2 r^2 \psi^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2})}{\psi^2}\right\}, \left\{j \rightarrow \frac{2 (\pi r \psi + \sqrt{\pi^2 r^2 \psi^2 - \pi^2 r^2 \psi^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2})}{\psi^2}\right\}\right\}$$

c := 2.99792458 (10^8)

$$\text{Solve}\left[r \text{Sin}[\beta] == \frac{\sqrt{4 j \pi r \psi - j^2 \psi^2}}{2 \pi}, v\right]$$

$$\text{Solve}\left[\frac{\sqrt{\psi} \sqrt{j} \sqrt{4 \pi r - j^2 \psi^2}}{2 \pi} == r \text{Sin}[\beta], r\right]$$

$$\left\{\left\{r \rightarrow \frac{\text{Csc}[\beta]^2 (4 j \pi \psi - 4 \sqrt{j^2 \pi^2 \psi^2 - j^3 \pi^2 \psi^3 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2})}{8 \pi^2}\right\}, \right. \\ \left. \left\{r \rightarrow \frac{j \pi \psi \text{Csc}[\beta]^2 + \text{Csc}[\beta]^2 \sqrt{j^2 \pi^2 \psi^2 - j^3 \pi^2 \psi^3 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}}{2 \pi^2}\right\}\right\}$$

$$\text{Solve}\left[\frac{\sqrt{\psi / \sqrt{1 - \frac{(v)^2}{c^2}}} \sqrt{j} \sqrt{1 - \frac{(v)^2}{c^2}} \sqrt{4 \pi r - j^2 \psi^2}}{2 \pi} == r \text{Sin}[\beta], v\right]$$

$$\left\{\left\{v \rightarrow -\left(\left(1. \sqrt{(-1.12941 \times 10^{18} j r \psi + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} j^3 \psi^3 + 3.54814 \times 10^{18} r^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)}\right) / \left(\sqrt{-12.5664 j r \psi + j^3 \psi^3 + 39.4784 r^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}\right)\right)\right\}, \right. \\ \left. \left\{v \rightarrow \frac{\sqrt{-1.12941 \times 10^{18} j r \psi + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} j^3 \psi^3 + 3.54814 \times 10^{18} r^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}}{\sqrt{-12.5664 j r \psi + j^3 \psi^3 + 39.4784 r^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}}\right\}\right\}$$

$$\left(\sqrt{(-1.1294090667581471 \cdot 10^{18} j r \psi + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} j^3 \psi^3 + 3.5481432270250993 \cdot 10^{18} r^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)}\right) / \left(\sqrt{-12.566370614359172 \cdot j r \psi + j^3 \psi^3 + 39.47841760435743 \cdot r^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}\right) ==$$

$$\text{Solve}\left[\frac{\sqrt{4 j \pi r \psi - j^2 \psi^2}}{2 \pi} == \frac{\sqrt{r \sqrt{1 - \frac{(v)^2}{c^2}}} \sqrt{\frac{\theta}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{(v)^2}{c^2}}}} \sqrt{4 \pi r - r \theta}}{2 \pi}, v\right]$$

$$\left\{\left\{v \rightarrow \frac{-\left(1. \sqrt{\left(-1.12941 \times 10^{18} r^2 \theta + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} r^2 \theta^2 + 1.12941 \times 10^{18} j r \psi - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} j^2 \psi^2\right)}{\left(\sqrt{-12.5664 r^2 \theta + r^2 \theta^2 + 12.5664 j r \psi - 1. j^2 \psi^2}\right)}\right\},\right.$$

$$\left.\left\{v \rightarrow \left(\sqrt{\left(-1.12941 \times 10^{18} r^2 \theta + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} r^2 \theta^2 + 1.12941 \times 10^{18} j r \psi - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} j^2 \psi^2\right)}\right) / \left(\sqrt{-12.5664 r^2 \theta + r^2 \theta^2 + 12.5664 j r \psi - 1. j^2 \psi^2}\right)\right\}\right\}$$

$$\text{Solve}\left[\left(\sqrt{\left(-1.1294090667581471 \cdot \cdot^{\wedge} 18 j r \psi + 8.987551787368176 \cdot \cdot^{\wedge} 16 j^3 \psi^3 + 3.5481432270250993 \cdot \cdot^{\wedge} 18 r^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2\right)}\right) / \left(\sqrt{-12.566370614359172 \cdot j r \psi + j^3 \psi^3 + 39.47841760435743 \cdot r^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}\right) == \left(\sqrt{\left(-1.1294090667581471 \cdot \cdot^{\wedge} 18 r^2 \theta + 8.987551787368176 \cdot \cdot^{\wedge} 16 r^2 \theta^2 + 1.1294090667581472 \cdot \cdot^{\wedge} 18 j r \psi - 8.987551787368176 \cdot \cdot^{\wedge} 16 j^2 \psi^2\right)}\right) / \left(\sqrt{\left(-12.566370614359172 \cdot r^2 \theta + r^2 \theta^2 + 12.566370614359172 \cdot j r \psi - 1. \cdot j^2 \psi^2\right)}\right), \beta\right]$$

$$\{\{\}\}$$

$$\text{Solve}[v == \left(\sqrt{\left(-1.1294090667581471 \cdot \cdot^{\wedge} 18 r^2 \theta + 8.987551787368176 \cdot \cdot^{\wedge} 16 r^2 \theta^2 + 1.1294090667581472 \cdot \cdot^{\wedge} 18 j r \psi - 8.987551787368176 \cdot \cdot^{\wedge} 16 j^2 \psi^2\right)}\right) / \left(\sqrt{\left(-12.566370614359172 \cdot r^2 \theta + r^2 \theta^2 + 12.566370614359172 \cdot j r \psi - 1. \cdot j^2 \psi^2\right)}\right), \psi]$$

$$\left\{\left\{\psi \rightarrow \left(0.5 \left(-1. j r \left(7.39612 \times 10^{32} - 8.22929 \times 10^{15} v^2\right) - 1. \sqrt{\left(j^2 r^2 \left(7.39612 \times 10^{32} - 8.22929 \times 10^{15} v^2\right)^2 - 4. j^2 r^2 \left(-5.88564 \times 10^{31} + 6.54866 \times 10^{14} v^2\right) \theta \left(-7.39612 \times 10^{32} + 8.22929 \times 10^{15} v^2 + 5.88564 \times 10^{31} \theta - 6.54866 \times 10^{14} v^2 \theta\right)\right)}\right)\right)\right) / \left(j^2 \left(-5.88564 \times 10^{31} + 6.54866 \times 10^{14} v^2\right)\right)\right\}, \left\{\psi \rightarrow \left(0.5 \left(-1. j r \left(7.39612 \times 10^{32} - 8.22929 \times 10^{15} v^2\right) + \sqrt{\left(j^2 r^2 \left(7.39612 \times 10^{32} - 8.22929 \times 10^{15} v^2\right)^2 - 4. j^2 r^2 \left(-5.88564 \times 10^{31} + 6.54866 \times 10^{14} v^2\right) \theta \left(-7.39612 \times 10^{32} + 8.22929 \times 10^{15} v^2 + 5.88564 \times 10^{31} \theta - 6.54866 \times 10^{14} v^2 \theta\right)\right)}\right)\right)\right) / \left(j^2 \left(-5.88564 \times 10^{31} + 6.54866 \times 10^{14} v^2\right)\right)\right\}\right\}$$

$$\frac{\sqrt{4 j \pi r \psi - j^2 \psi^2}}{2 \pi} == \frac{\sqrt{4 \pi r^2 \theta - r^2 \theta^2}}{2 \pi} == \frac{r \sqrt{\gamma} \sqrt{4 \pi + \gamma}}{\sqrt{4 \pi^2 + 4 \pi \gamma + \gamma^2}}$$

$$\text{Solve}\left[\frac{\sqrt{4 j \pi r \psi - j^2 \psi^2}}{2 \pi} == \frac{\sqrt{4 \pi r^2 \theta - r^2 \theta^2}}{2 \pi}, j\right]$$

$$\left\{\left\{j \rightarrow \frac{r \theta}{\psi}\right\}, \left\{j \rightarrow \frac{4 \pi r - r \theta}{\psi}\right\}\right\}$$

$$\text{Solve}\left[\frac{\sqrt{4 j \pi r \psi - j^2 \psi^2}}{2 \pi} == \frac{r \sqrt{\gamma} \sqrt{4 \pi + \gamma}}{\sqrt{4 \pi^2 + 4 \pi \gamma + \gamma^2}}, j\right]$$

$$\left\{\left\{j \rightarrow \frac{2 \pi r \gamma}{(2 \pi + \gamma) \psi}\right\}, \left\{j \rightarrow \frac{2 (4 \pi^2 r + \pi r \gamma)}{(2 \pi + \gamma) \psi}\right\}\right\}$$

$$\text{Solve}[2 \pi r - 2 \pi x == \psi j, x]$$

$$\left\{\left\{x \rightarrow \frac{2 \pi r - j \psi}{2 \pi}\right\}\right\}$$

$$\text{Solve}\left[\frac{\sqrt{4 j \pi r \psi - j^2 \psi^2}}{2 \pi} == n / (n + 1), n\right]$$

$$\left\{\left\{n \rightarrow \frac{\sqrt{-j \psi (-4 \pi r + j \psi)}}{2 \pi - \sqrt{-j \psi (-4 \pi r + j \psi)}}\right\}\right\}$$

$$\frac{\sqrt{-j \psi (-4 \pi r + j \psi)}}{2 \pi - \sqrt{-j \psi (-4 \pi r + j \psi)}}$$

$$\text{Solve}\left[\frac{2 \pi r - j \psi}{2 \pi} \wedge \frac{\sqrt{-j \psi (-4 \pi r + j \psi)}}{2 \pi - \sqrt{-j \psi (-4 \pi r + j \psi)}} + \frac{\sqrt{4 j \pi r \psi - j^2 \psi^2}}{2 \pi} \wedge \frac{\sqrt{-j \psi (-4 \pi r + j \psi)}}{2 \pi - \sqrt{-j \psi (-4 \pi r + j \psi)}} == r \wedge \frac{\sqrt{-j \psi (-4 \pi r + j \psi)}}{2 \pi - \sqrt{-j \psi (-4 \pi r + j \psi)}}, \psi\right]$$

$$\text{Solve}\left[(2 \pi)^{-\frac{\sqrt{-j \psi (-4 \pi r + j \psi)}}{2 \pi - \sqrt{-j \psi (-4 \pi r + j \psi)}}} (2 \pi r - j \psi)^{\frac{\sqrt{-j \psi (-4 \pi r + j \psi)}}{2 \pi - \sqrt{-j \psi (-4 \pi r + j \psi)}}} + (2 \pi)^{-\frac{\sqrt{-j \psi (-4 \pi r + j \psi)}}{2 \pi - \sqrt{-j \psi (-4 \pi r + j \psi)}}} (4 j \pi r \psi - j^2 \psi^2)^{\frac{\sqrt{-j \psi (-4 \pi r + j \psi)}}{2 \pi - \sqrt{-j \psi (-4 \pi r + j \psi)}}} == r^{2 \pi - \frac{\sqrt{-j \psi (-4 \pi r + j \psi)}}{2 \pi - \sqrt{-j \psi (-4 \pi r + j \psi)}}}, \psi\right]$$

$$\text{Solve}\left[\frac{\sqrt{\psi / \sqrt{1 - \frac{(v)^2}{c^2}}} \sqrt{j \sqrt{1 - \frac{(v)^2}{c^2}}} \sqrt{4 \pi r - j^2 \psi^2}}{2 \pi} == r \text{Sin}[\beta], v\right]$$

$$\left\{\left\{v \rightarrow -\left(\left(1. \sqrt{(-1.12941 \times 10^{18} j r \psi + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} j^3 \psi^3 + 3.54814 \times 10^{18} r^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)}\right) / \left(\sqrt{-12.5664 j r \psi + j^3 \psi^3 + 39.4784 r^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}\right)\right)\right\},\right.$$

$$\left.\left\{v \rightarrow \frac{\sqrt{-1.12941 \times 10^{18} j r \psi + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} j^3 \psi^3 + 3.54814 \times 10^{18} r^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}}{\sqrt{-12.5664 j r \psi + j^3 \psi^3 + 39.4784 r^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2}}\right\}\right\}$$

$$\frac{1}{2(j^2 + 4j^2\pi)} \left(4j\pi + 8j\pi^2 r - 8j\pi^2 \sqrt{-h^2 + r^2} + \sqrt{\left(-4j\pi - 8j\pi^2 r + 8j\pi^2 \sqrt{-h^2 + r^2}\right)^2 - 16\pi^2(j^2 + 4j^2\pi)r\text{Sin}[\beta]^2} \right)$$

$h := r \text{Sin}[\beta]$

Solve $\left[\psi == \frac{1}{2(j^2 + 4j^2\pi)} \left(4j\pi + 8j\pi^2 r - 8j\pi^2 \sqrt{-h^2 + r^2} + \sqrt{\left(-4j\pi - 8j\pi^2 r + 8j\pi^2 \sqrt{-h^2 + r^2}\right)^2 - 16\pi^2(j^2 + 4j^2\pi)r\text{Sin}[\beta]^2} \right), \beta \right]$

$\left\{ \left\{ \beta \rightarrow -\text{ArcSin} \left[\frac{1}{2} \sqrt{\left(8j\psi + \frac{4j\psi}{\pi r} - 8j^2\psi^2 - \frac{j^2\psi^2}{\pi^2 r} - \frac{4j^2\psi^2}{\pi r} - \frac{1}{\pi r^2} \right)} \right] \right\} \right\}$

$4 \sqrt{\left(j^2 r^3 \psi^2 (4\pi^2 r - 4j\pi\psi - 8j\pi^2 r\psi + j^2\psi^2 + 4j^2\pi\psi^2 + 4j^2\pi^2 r\psi^2) \right)}$

$\left\{ \left\{ \beta \rightarrow \text{ArcSin} \left[\frac{1}{2} \sqrt{\left(8j\psi + \frac{4j\psi}{\pi r} - 8j^2\psi^2 - \frac{j^2\psi^2}{\pi^2 r} - \frac{4j^2\psi^2}{\pi r} - \frac{1}{\pi r^2} \right)} \right] \right\} \right\}$

$4 \sqrt{\left(j^2 r^3 \psi^2 (4\pi^2 r - 4j\pi\psi - 8j\pi^2 r\psi + j^2\psi^2 + 4j^2\pi\psi^2 + 4j^2\pi^2 r\psi^2) \right)}$

$\left\{ \left\{ \beta \rightarrow -\text{ArcSin} \left[\sqrt{\left(2j\psi + \frac{j\psi}{\pi r} - 2j^2\psi^2 - \frac{j^2\psi^2}{4\pi^2 r} - \frac{j^2\psi^2}{\pi r} + \frac{1}{\pi r^2} \right)} \left(\sqrt{\left(4j^2\pi^2 r^4 \psi^2 - 4j^3\pi r^3 \psi^3 - 8j^3\pi^2 r^4 \psi^3 + \frac{j^4(1024\pi^6 + 4096\pi^7)r^3\psi^4}{1024\pi^6} + 4j^4\pi^2 r^4 \psi^4 \right)} \right) \right] \right\} \right\}$

$\left\{ \left\{ \beta \rightarrow \text{ArcSin} \left[\sqrt{\left(2j\psi + \frac{j\psi}{\pi r} - 2j^2\psi^2 - \frac{j^2\psi^2}{4\pi^2 r} - \frac{j^2\psi^2}{\pi r} + \frac{1}{\pi r^2} \right)} \left(\sqrt{\left(4j^2\pi^2 r^4 \psi^2 - 4j^3\pi r^3 \psi^3 - 8j^3\pi^2 r^4 \psi^3 + \frac{j^4(1024\pi^6 + 4096\pi^7)r^3\psi^4}{1024\pi^6} + 4j^4\pi^2 r^4 \psi^4 \right)} \right) \right] \right\} \right\}$